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GRAU EN ENGINYERIA DE SISTEMES DE TELECOMUNICACIÓ

ANALOG BEAMFORMING IN MMWAVE MASSIVE MIMO SYSTEMS WITH 1-BIT ADC

Rubén Morales Ferré

DIRECTOR: Gonzalo Seco Granados

DEPARTAMENT DE TELECOMUNICACIÓ I ENGINYERIA DE SISTEMES

UNIVERSITAT AUTÒNOMA DE BARCELONA

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El tribunal d'avaluació d'aquest Treball Fi de Grau, reunit el dia 18 de Juliol de 2016, ha acordat concedir la següent qualificació:

President: Gonzalo Seco Granados

Vocal: José A. López-Salcedo

Secretari: Simona Lohan

Els sotasignant, Gonzalo Seco Granados, Professor de l'Escola d'Enginyeria de la Universitat Autònoma de Barcelona (UAB),

CERTIFICA:

Que el projecte presentat en aquesta memòria de Treball Fi de Grau ha estat realitzat sota la seva direcció per l'alumne Rubén Morales Ferré.

I, perquè consti a tots els efectes, signa el present certificat.

Bellaterra, 11 de Juliol de 2016.

Signatura:

Summary:

This document describes a millimeter wave (with carriers about 60 GHz) massive MIMO (Multiple Input Multiple Output) communication system with analog beamforming at the receiver. It is only considered the uplink communication between K single-antenna users, which transmit with QPSK modulation, and a massive antenna grouping Base Station (BS). The BS makes use of a beamformer as a previous step to quantize the received signal, in order to be able to select the transmission made by a single user, instead all the transmission added. It also uses a 1-bit Analog-to-Digital converter (ADC) to quantise the received signal, which is simple and more power efficient than ADC's of larger order.

In order to evaluate the performance of the system and be able to compare the benefits of using analog beamforming, we will calculate the Symbol Error Rate (SER) and the Mutual Information between the sent and received symbols. Then we will compare different receive filters and different lengths of the pilot sequences in the channel estimation. It is also shown two methods to evaluate the performance metrics, by means of Monte Carlo simulations, and an analytical approach.

Resum:

En aquest document es descriu un sistema de comunicacions MIMO (Multiple Input Multiple Output) massiu a la banda d'ones mil·limètriques (amb portadores de l'ordre de 60 GHz) amb beamforming analògic. Només s'ha tingut en compte la comunicació uplink entre K usuaris amb una sola antena, els quals transmeten mitjançant la modulació QPSK, i una estació base (BS) amb agrupació massiva d'antenes. La BS fa us de beamforming com a pas previ a la quantificació del senyal, amb la finalitat de poder seleccionar les transmissions fetes per cadascun dels usuaris. A més, s'utilitza un conversor Analògic-Digital (ADC) d'un bit per a quantificar la senyal, el qual és més senzill y eficient en quant a consum energètic que no pas un ADC de major ordre.

Per avaluar les prestacions del sistema y ser capaços de comparar els beneficis del beamforming, es calcularà el Symbol Error Rate (SER) y la Informació Mútua entre els símbols enviats i rebuts. Amb aquest objectiu es mostraran dos mètodes diferents per avaluar la SER y la informació mútua, el primer mitjançant simulacions de Monte Carlo, y el segon a partir d'una aproximació analítica. S'utilitzaran diferents filtres de recepció, a més de diferents longituds de les seqüències pilot a l'estimació de canal.

Resumen:

En este documento se describe un sistema de comunicaciones MIMO (Multiple Input Multiple Output) masivo en la banda de ondas milimétricas (con portadoras del orden de 60 GHz) con beamforming analógico. Solo se ha tenido en cuenta la comunicación uplink entre K usuarios con una sola antena, los cuales transmiten con modulación QPSK, y una estación base (BS) con agrupación masiva de antenas. La BS hace uso de beamforming como paso previo a la cuantificación del señal, con la finalidad de poder seleccionar las transmisiones hechas por cada usuario. además, se utiliza un conversor Analógico-Digital (ADC) de un bit para cuantificar el señal, el cual es más sencillo y eficiente en cuanto a consumo energético que uno de mayor orden.

Para evaluar las prestaciones del sistema y ser capaces de comparar los beneficios del beamforming, se calculará el Symbol Error Rate (SER) y la información mutua entre los símbolos enviados y recibidos. Para ello se mostraran dos métodos diferentes para evaluar la SER y la información mutua, el primero mediante simulaciones de Monte Carlo, y el segundo a partir de una aproximación analítica. Se utilizaran diferentes filtros de recepción y longitudes de secuencias piloto en la estimación de canal.

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Contents

Abstract	i
Acknowledgement	iii
List of Figures	x
1 Introduction	1
1.1 Objectives	5
1.2 Methodology	5
1.3 Document structure	6
2 System model	9
2.1 System model description without Beamforming	9
2.1.1 Received signal at the base station	11
2.1.2 Fading Rayleigh channel and channel estimation	11
2.1.3 Quantization	12
2.1.4 Symbol estimation	13
2.2 MmWave channel model	14
2.2.1 MmWave channel model description: The clustered channel model	14
2.3 System model description with Beamforming	18
2.3.1 Model description	18
2.3.2 Analog Beamforming	19

3	Performance metrics	23
3.1	Monte Carlo simulations	23
3.1.1	Symbol Error Rate	23
3.1.2	Mutual Information	24
3.2	Analytical approach	24
3.2.1	Symbol Error Rate	27
3.2.2	Mutual Information	28
3.3	Numerical and analytical methods comparison	28
4	Results	31
4.1	Symbol Error Rate	31
4.1.1	SER with no analog beamforming applied	31
4.1.2	SER with analog beamforming applied	35
4.2	Mutual Information	45
4.2.1	Mutual Information with no analog beamforming applied	45
4.2.2	Mutual Information with analog beamforming applied	49
5	Conclusions	57
A	Matlab code	61
	Bibliography	

List of Figures

1.1	Atmospheric absorption across mm-wave frequencies in dB/km (above), and Atmospheric absorption across mm-wave frequencies in dB/km (below).	3
1.2	Uplink of a multi-cell massive MIMO system.	4
1.3	Uplink of a multi-cell massive MIMO system.	6
2.1	Block diagram of the system model without beamforming.	10
2.2	System model without beamforming.	10
2.3	Truncated Laplacian PDF with $\mu = 0$ and $\sigma^2 = 1$	15
2.4	Truncated Laplacian PDF with $\mu = 0$ and $\sigma^2 = 0.1$	16
2.5	Example of clustered channel model with 1 user, 2 rays per user and 2 clusters.	17
2.6	System model with beamforming.	19
2.7	System model with beamforming. Beamforming box is divided in the steering matrix R and correction matrix D	19
2.8	Example of 1 user, 2 cluster and 3 beams per cluster.	20
3.1	SER per user versus SNR considering $M = 400$ and $K = 20$, and the MRC filter with full CSI. Monte Carlo symbol and noise vectors simulation results are compared with the analytical results based on 20 and 31.	28
3.2	Mutual Information per user versus SNR considering $M = 400$ and $K = 20$, and the MRC filter with full CSI. Monte Carlo symbol and noise vectors simulation results are compared with the analytical results based on 20 and 19.	29

4.1	SER per user versus SNR for $M=400$ and $K=20$. The ZF and MRC filters are considered for both the cases of perfect and imperfect CSI. The training sequence length depends on the number of users K . The fading channel model has been used.	32
4.2	SER per user versus SNR for $M=400$ and $K=20$. The ZF and MRC filters are considered for both the cases of perfect and imperfect CSI. The training sequence length depends on the number of antennas M . The fading channel model has been used.	33
4.3	SER per user versus SNR for $M=400$ and $K=20$. The ZF and MRC filters are considered for both the cases of perfect and imperfect CSI. The training sequence length depends on the number of antennas K . The mmWave channel model has been used with 2 clusters per user and 10 rays per cluster.	34
4.4	SER per user versus SNR for $M=200$ and $K=10$. The ZF and MRC filters are considered for both the cases of perfect and imperfect CSI. The training sequence length depends on the number of antennas K . The mmWave channel model has been used with 2 clusters per user and 10 rays per cluster.	34
4.5	SER per user versus SNR for $M=100$ and $K=5$. The ZF and MRC filters are considered for both the cases of perfect and imperfect CSI. The training sequence length depends on the number of antennas K . The mmWave channel model has been used with 2 clusters per user and 10 rays per cluster.	35
4.6	SER per user versus SNR for $M=200$ and $K=10$. It is considered 2 cluster per user, 10 rays per cluster, 6 beam per cluster, beam separation 0.4° deg and Laplacian PDF standard deviation 0.25. The ZF and MRC filters are considered for both the cases of perfect and imperfect CSI. .	36
4.7	SER per user versus SNR for $M=100$ and $K=5$. It is considered 2 cluster per user, 10 rays per cluster, 5 beam per cluster, beam separation 0.1° deg and Laplacian PDF standard deviation 0.25. The ZF and MRC filters are considered for both the cases of perfect and imperfect CSI. .	37
4.8	SER per user versus SNR for $M=100$ and $K=5$. It is considered 2 cluster per user, 10 rays per cluster, 10 beam per cluster, beam separation 0.1° deg and Laplacian PDF standard deviation 0.25. The ZF and MRC filters are considered for both the cases of perfect and imperfect CSI. .	37
4.9	SER per user versus SNR for $M=100$ and $K=5$. It is considered 3 different cases, 2 with beamforming and another without it. We also consider 2 cluster per user, 10 rays per cluster, 5 or 10 beam per cluster, beam separation 1° deg and Laplacian PDF standard deviation 0.25. The ZF and MRC filters are considered for imperfect CSI with $N = 50K$ pilot training length. .	39
4.10	SER per user versus SNR for $M=100$ and $K=5$. It is considered the case with beamforming and 10 beams and without beamforming. The MRC (above) and ZF (below) filters are considered for both the cases of perfect and imperfect CSI.	40

4.11	SER per user versus SNR for $M=100$ and $K=5$. It is considered the system with beamforming and 8 beams and without beamforming. The MRC (top) and ZF (bottom) filters are considered for both the cases of perfect and imperfect CSI.	41
4.12	SER per user versus SNR for $M=100$ and $K=5$. It is considered the case with beamforming and 8 beams with and without apply the phase correction matrix D . The MRC (top) and ZF (bottom) filters are considered for both the cases of perfect and imperfect CSI.	42
4.13	SER per user versus SNR for $M=100$ and $K=5$. It is considered the case with beamforming and 8 beams using two different Laplace PDF standard deviation, $\sigma = 0.1$ and $\sigma = 1$. The MRC (top) and ZF (bottom) filters are considered for both the cases of perfect and imperfect CSI.	44
4.14	Mutual Information versus SNR for $M=400$ and $K=20$. The ZF and MRC filters are considered for both the cases of perfect and imperfect CSI. The training sequence length depends on the number of users K .The fading channel model has been used.	46
4.15	Mutual Information versus SNR for $M=400$ and $K=20$. The ZF and MRC filters are considered for both the cases of perfect and imperfect CSI. The training sequence length depends on the number of antennas M .The fading channel model has been used.	46
4.16	Mutual Information versus SNR for $M=400$ and $K=20$. The ZF and MRC filters are considered for both the cases of perfect and imperfect CSI. The training sequence length depends on the number of users K . The mmWave channel model has been used.	47
4.17	Mutual Information versus SNR for $M=200$ and $K=10$.The ZF and MRC filters are considered for both the cases of perfect and imperfect CSI. The training sequence length depends on the number of users K .The mmWave channel model has been used.	48
4.18	Mutual Information versus SNR for $M=100$ and $K=5$.The ZF and MRC filters are considered for both the cases of perfect and imperfect CSI. The training sequence length depends on the number of users K .The mmWave channel model has been used.	49
4.19	Mutual Information versus SNR for $M=200$ and $K=10$. It is considered 2 cluster per user, 10 rays per cluster, 6 beam per cluster, beam separation 0.4° deg and Laplacian PDF standard deviation 0.25. The ZF and MRC filters are considered for both the cases of perfect and imperfect CSI.	50
4.20	Mutual Information versus SNR or $M=100$ and $K=5$. It is considered 2 cluster per user, 10 rays per cluster, 5 beam per cluster, beam separation 0.1° deg and Laplacian PDF standard deviation 0.25. The ZF and MRC filters are considered for both the cases of perfect and imperfect CSI.	51
4.21	Mutual Information versus SNR or $M=100$ and $K=5$. It is considered 2 cluster per user, 10 rays per cluster, 10 beam per cluster, beam separation 0.1° deg and Laplacian PDF standard deviation 0.25. The ZF and MRC filters are considered for both the cases of perfect and imperfect CSI.	52

4.22	Mutual Information versus SNR for $M=100$ and $K=5$. It is considered 3 different cases, 2 with beamforming and another without it. We also consider 2 cluster per user, 10 rays per cluster, 5 or 10 beam per cluster, beam separation 1° deg and Laplacian PDF standard deviation 0.25. The ZF and MRC filters are considered for both imperfect CSI with $N = 50K$ pilot training length.	52
4.23	Mutual Information per user versus SNR for $M=100$ and $K=5$. It is considered the case with beamforming and 10 beams and without beamforming. The MRC (top) and ZF (bottom) filters are considered for both the cases of perfect and imperfect CSI.	53
4.24	Mutual Information per user versus SNR for $M=100$ and $K=5$. It is considered the case with beamforming and 8 beams and without beamforming. The MRC (top) and ZF (bottom) filters are considered for both the cases of perfect and imperfect CSI.	54
4.25	Mutual Information per user versus SNR for $M=100$ and $K=5$. It is considered the case with beamforming and 8 beams with and without apply the phase correction matrix D . The MRC (top) and ZF (bottom) filters are considered for both the cases of perfect and imperfect CSI.	55
4.26	Mutual Information per user versus SNR for $M=100$ and $K=5$. It is considered the case with beamforming and 8 beams using two different Laplace PDF standard deviation, $\sigma = 0.1$ and $\sigma = 1$. The MRC (top) and ZF (bottom) filters are considered for both the cases of perfect and imperfect CSI.	56

1 Introduction

In the future 5G communications systems, it is considering the possibility to use millimeter waves (from now on mmWave) and massive MIMO (Multiple Input Multiple Output) large-scale Antenna systems, in order to satisfy the high volumes of wireless data required and the increasing number of users. That means change the traditional frequency bands and use the Extremely high frequency (EHF) band, with a carrier frequency from 30 GHz to 300 GHz and equipping cellular base stations (BSs) with a very large number of antennas. The massive MIMO system is composed by multiple antennas (e.g., 400 antennas, or an order of magnitude more antennas than users) in the BS that simultaneously serves a set of single-antenna users (typically a few of them, e.g., 20 users). That is shown in Figure 1.2, where we have represented a set of 3 cells, with a few users per cell, who are communicating with the BS in each cell composed by M antennas. The huge number of antennas in the BS is the reason for using the mmWave band, since the dimensions of the antennas are considerably smaller in mmWave than in the traditional transmission bands. That's because the physical dimensions of the antennas are inversely proportional to the frequency of operation. So increasing the frequency of operation means decrease the wavelength, and hence it permit us use smaller antennas, since the physical dimensions of the antenna depends directly of the wavelength. By that way is more realisable to have a large number of antennas at the BS, because as they are smaller, we are able to have more antennas in the same device area.

There are some advantages by using mmWave and massive MIMO, but we can also found a few disadvantages. We show some of them:

Advantages:

- Since the number of antennas at the BS is typically assumed to be significantly larger than the number of users, a large number of degrees of freedom are available, and can be used to shape the transmitted signals in a hardware-friendly way or to null interference. [1]
- Each single-antenna user in a massive MIMO system can scale down its transmit

power, proportional to the number of antennas at the BS with perfect channel state information (CSI), or to the square root of the number of BS antennas with imperfect CSI, to get the same performance as a corresponding SISO (Single Input Single Output) system. So massive MIMO systems are potentially more energy efficient compared to a corresponding SISO systems. [1]

- The expensive equipment is only needed on the BS end of the link, and the user terminals can be relatively cheap single-antenna. devices[1]

- Due to multi-user diversity, the performance of massive MIMO systems is generally less sensitive to the propagation environment than in the point-to-point MIMO case. [1]

- Mmwave carrier frequencies allow for larger bandwidth allocations, which is translated directly to higher data transfer rates. [1]

- By increasing the RF channel bandwidth, the data capacity is greatly increased, while the latency for digital traffic is hugely decreased, thus supporting much better internet-based access and applications that require minimal latency. [1]

- Less congestion on the frequency bands at mmWave frequencies. The spectrum is less crowded at mmWave frequencies, hence less saturated and it can offer a better performance.

Disadvantages:

- Attenuation due to rain and atmospheric and molecular absorption of communication at mmWave frequencies is larger than using lower carrier frequencies, as it is showed in Figure 1.1. However, it is considering that cell sizes (in urban environments) will be around 200m. So due to the cell size, the mmWave communications are not so affected as it can seem. For cell sizes on the order of 200 m, atmospheric absorption or rain loss do not create significant additional path loss for mmWaves. E.g. at 60 GHz, as it is showed in the inferior part of Figure 1.1, less than 10 dB/km of attenuation is expected due to heavy rainfall rates of 25 mm/hr for cellular propagation, which translates to only 2 dB of attenuation over 200 m distance of the cell. The same happens about the atmospheric absorption and free space propagation loss, as it is showed in the superior part of Figure 1.1, only 3 dB, even though the Oxygen absorption in the 60 GHz band has a peak, and 5.6 dB more than at 2.4 GHz, respectively. So for small distances (less than 1 km), rain

attenuation and atmosphere will present a minimal effect on the propagation of mm-waves for small cells. Even that attenuation can actually be beneficial in small-cell scenarios, since it limits the inter-cell interferences and allows greater frequency reuse. [1]

- The fact that in most of the cases mmWave signals do not penetrate brick and concrete, means that mmWave cells may have to be located strictly indoors or strictly outdoors, a factor that could limit their application. [1]

- It's needed more research on RF chains, electronics and antenna design and other devices and techniques in order to manage the communications systems more efficiently. Most of the developed systems are produced for lower mmWave frequencies (a few GHz). And due the peculiarities of mmWave high frequencies, is needed to adapt and develop new efficient techniques and devices [1].

Figure 1.1: Atmospheric absorption across mm-wave frequencies in dB/km (above), and Atmospheric absorption across mm-wave frequencies in dB/km (below).

Figure 1.2: Uplink of a multi-cell massive MIMO system.

In consideration of reduce the power consumption provoked by the large number of antennas employed at the BS and other devices, it is proposed to use 1-bit Analog-to-digital converters (1-bit ADC). The use of 1-bit ADC consumes less power than bigger order ADCs, so they are more power efficient due to their lower complexity. But 1-bit ADCs produce a larger number of errors during the quantization process than using bigger order ADCs, in view of the fact that, principally, the accuracy of it depends on the chosen ADC bit resolution.

One method utilized to try to correct this, and reduce the number of errors caused by the 1-bit ADC, is using analog beamforming as a previous step to quantify the received signal. By that way, it could be possible to address the beam to a single user, and receive the information sent by him, instead of receive all the users transmissions added. Therefore, the number of errors would be significantly reduced, since quantifying a single QPSK signal with a 1-bit ADC produces reasonably fewer errors than quantifying a combination of QPSK signals from the different users.

So, the main objective of this document is to show the improvements by using analog beamforming prior the 1 bit ADC quantification. In order to do that and be able to compare the performance of using and not using analog beamforming, it is computed the Symbol Error Rate (SER) and the Mutual Information, and so it is compared the case with and without analog beamforming. Furthermore, it is show two ways of compute it: The analytical, which is computed by doing an analytical approach of the transmission system, and the numerical, which is computed through several simulations of the transmission system. In addition, it is presented a mmWave channel model, which tries to fit the mmWave main features into the system pre-

sented. Finally are tried different values of the beamforming parameters in order to show the performance of it.

1.1 Objectives

The main objective of this project is to implement, using MATLAB, an uplink massive MIMO communication system with 1-bit ADC, apply analog beamforming in the receiver and then show the improvements by using it. The more detailed objectives are:

- Understand and be able to implement the system model shown in [2].
- Be able to understand and implement in MATLAB the analytical approach shown in [2], in order to avoid the use of Monte Carlo Simulations, and hence, reduce the computational complexity of the system implementation.
- Implement a channel model that fits the channel at mmWave frequency band, which is shown in [3], [4] and [5].
- Implement the analog beamforming system at the receiver shown in [6].
- Compute the chosen performance metrics, the SER and the Mutual Information, by both the Monte Carlo simulations and the analytical approach, and using analog beamforming and without it. And then analyse the obtained results by comparing the performance of using and not using analog beamforming and get conclusions.

1.2 Methodology

To implement this project, we have made use of MATLAB. Basically, it is composed of a MATLAB GUI, with which you can choose the principal parameters of the simulation, such as the number of users and the number of receiver antennas, the total number of Monte Carlo simulations, and the beamforming parameters such as the number of clusters, the number of beams per cluster and the angular separation between beams. Then you need to select what kind of result you want to compute (SER or Mutual Information, with or without beamforming), what channel model to use and the length of the pilots in the channel estimation. Finally you must select the method to compute the performance metrics, using Monte Carlo Simulations or by the analytical approach. If both are selected at the end of the simulation a comparison between the two methods is depicted.

Once you have selected the options to simulate and chosen the system parameters, you can click the OK button, and then the simulation began. After the simulation ends, a plot with the desire result is shown. With the CANCEL button you can stop the simulation.

Figure 1.3: Uplink of a multi-cell massive MIMO system.

1.3 Document structure

The objective of this first chapter is give a global vision of the entire project. Firstly it is shown a background and state of the art of massive MIMO and mmWave systems. Then are shown the proposed objectives of the project, and finally, a brief overview about the key features of the project and methodologies of implementation.

In the second chapter, is presented a general overview of the implemented communication system. Firstly, it is shown the system model without beamforming. Are shown the main features of the received signal at the base station, the channel estimation, the quantization of the received signal and the received filter computation and symbol estimation, among other things. Then are presented the distinctive features of mmWave channels, and is explained the chosen channel model that tries to fit the features of the mWaves into our system. Finally it is showed the system model with analog beamforming, and are explained the technical differences between using and not using analog beamforming.

In the third chapter are presented the chosen performance metrics, the SER and the Mutual Information. It is shown how both are calculated by two ways, numerically by using Monte

Carlo simulations, and analytically by using an analytical approach. Then both are compared in order to show the accuracy of the analytical approach.

In the fourth chapter are presented the results of the project. It is divided in two blocks, the results for the SER and the results for the Mutual Information, both with and without analog beamforming applied. The results for different system parameters are shown in order to be able to compare the performance of the system.

In the last chapter is presented a whole overview of the project, and the conclusion of it.

Finally, in the appendix it is showed the MATLAB code used to produce the project. Are shown the functions that compose the project and some added commentaries, in order to do the code more understandable.

The notation in this document is:

- We use boldface lowercase to denote vectors and uppercase letters to designate matrices.
- \mathbf{X}^H is the hermitian transposed matrix of \mathbf{X} .
- \mathbf{X}^T is the transposed matrix of \mathbf{X} .
- $\hat{\mathbf{X}}^\dagger$ is the pseudoinverse (or Moore–Penrose pseudoinverse) of the matrix \mathbf{X} .
- $\|\mathbf{x}\|$ is the l_2 norm (or Euclidean norm) of \mathbf{x} .

2 System model

In this section, it is introduced the system model used to develop the project. Firstly, in section 2.1, we introduce the system model without beamforming. We show the different parts and signals that is composed the model, such as the received signal at the base station, the channel estimation procedure, the quantization process of the receive symbols and the symbol estimation at the receiver.

In section 2.2 it is shown the model channel used to fit the channel into the system using mmWave frequencies. It is also described the procedure to obtain it and the different parts that it is composed. The mmWaves as we have said before, it has some peculiarities that need to be reflected into the channel performance.

Finally, in section 2.3, it is presented the system model with beamforming, which is quite similar to the model seen in 2.1 but with some differences that are detailed. We present the differences and the procedure to compute the analog beamforming and obtain the received symbols sent by the users.

2.1 System model description without Beamforming

We consider a single-cell uplink system (transmission scenario where the users transmit signals to the BS), where there are K single-antenna users and one BS equipped with an array of M antennas. The channel model taken into account in this section is the fading Rayleigh channel, but it can be also extrapolated to mmWave channel, as we will show later. We consider a 1-bit ADC, which do not need energy-consuming interfaces such as automatic gain control (AGC). About the symbol estimation, it is based on two different receive filters, the Maximal Ratio Combining (MRC) and the Zero-Forcing (ZF). Finally, it is explained the procedure to estimate the channel by means of pilot sequences (or training sequences).

In Figure 2.1 is shown the box model of the system, where is represented the different parts of it. The different signals involved (above the arrows) and the dimensions of that signals (under the arrows) are shown. In the following subsections are explained the details of each one of this

blocks, in order to be able to understand the functioning of the core system. Summarizing Figure 2.1, it is shown as the K users transmit their symbols (Signal \mathbf{x}), then is applied the channel effect and added the AWGN noise. After that, the symbols are received by the M antennas at the BS and they are quantized. Finally, the received symbols are estimated by the receive filter \mathbf{A} .

Figure 2.1: Block diagram of the system model without beamforming.

Figure 2.2: System model without beamforming.

2.1.1 Received signal at the base station

The discrete-time complex baseband received signal at the base station is defined as

$$\mathbf{r} = \sqrt{P_t} \mathbf{H} \mathbf{x} + \mathbf{n}, \quad (1)$$

where $\mathbf{H} \in \mathbb{C}^{M \times K}$ is the channel matrix between the Base Station (BS), composed by M antennas, and the K users. It means that h_{mk} is the channel coefficient between the k -th user and the m -th antenna of the BS. Each h_{mk} is independent and follows a $\mathcal{CN}(0, 1)$ distribution. The vector $\mathbf{x} \in \mathbb{C}^K$ contains the transmitted symbols from all the users in a determined time instant. It means that the i -th entry of \mathbf{x} , x_i , is the symbol transmitted by user i . The symbols belong to a QPSK constellation, since the spectral efficiency in a massive MIMO system is typically low. Therefore, the possible transmitted symbols are: $\frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}(1 + 1j)$, $\frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}(-1 + 1j)$, $\frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}(-1 - 1j)$ and $\frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}(1 - 1j)$.

The P_t is the transmit power per user. Finally, the \mathbf{n} is the noise vector, which is independent and identically distributed zero-mean circularly symmetric complex Gaussian random variables, which is denoted by $\mathcal{CN}(0, \sigma_N^2)$.

2.1.2 Fading Rayleigh channel and channel estimation

In most communication systems, considerable distances separate the transmitter and receiver; therefore, the estimator at the receiver does not have practical access to the transmitted signal that enters the channel, so it is a priori unknown to the receiver.

We have supposed two cases. On the one hand, when we know the channel state information (CSI), called full CSI, which would be an ideal case. On the other hand, when we don't know the CSI in advance, and we need to estimate it. The CSI describes how a signal propagates from the transmitter to the receiver, and how the signal is modified when travels through the channel. So, the CSI makes it possible to adapt transmissions to current channel conditions.

In the first case, the full CSI channel, is considered that the CSI is known by the receiver. The entries of \mathbf{H} are independent $\mathcal{CN}(0, 1)$ random variables.

In the second case, we don't have previously channel information, so we need to estimate the channel. For CSI acquisition, three classes of methods are available:

1. The Blind Method. In this method, estimation of CSI merely is from the received data.
2. The Differential Ones. This method approach bypass CSI estimation by differential encoding

3. The Training-based Method. This method estimates CSI by the knowing training sequence.

Among them, the training based ones are the most attractive as they can decouple the demodulation/decoding from the CSI estimation and simplify significantly the structure of the receiver.

Therefore, the channel information needed to compute the channel estimation is acquired through sending uplink pilots. In particular, each coherence time of the channel is divided in two parts. During the first part of it, the users transmit pilot symbols from which the base station calculates the channel. During the remainder of the coherence time, all the users transmit their data to the BS, which in turn uses the receive filter calculated from the channel estimation through uplink pilots to detect the symbols and reconstruct the transmitted symbols. Moreover, we assume 1-bit analog-to-digital conversion even during the reception of the pilots.

The LS estimate of \mathbf{H} is shown in [2], and is given by

$$\hat{\mathbf{H}} = \left(\sum_{n=1}^N \sqrt{P_t} \mathbf{y}^{(n)} \mathbf{x}^{(n)H} \right) \left(\sum_{n=1}^N P_t \mathbf{x}^{(n)} \mathbf{x}^{(n)H} \right)^{-1}. \quad (2)$$

In (2), N is the number of time instances used for the pilot transmission, while $\mathbf{x}^{(n)}$ is the transmitted vector, and $\mathbf{y}^{(n)}$ is the quantized received vector, both at the n -th time instance dedicated to the training transmission.

Remark that we need at least K training symbol transmissions for the matrix $\sum_{n=1}^N P_t \mathbf{x}^{(n)} \mathbf{x}^{(n)H}$ to be invertible. The considered training length sequences N will be: $50K$, $10K$, $5K$, $50M$, $10M$ and $5M$, where K is the number of users and M is the number of antennas in the BS. Both accomplish the condition of $N < K$.

To conclude, we refer to $\hat{\mathbf{H}} = \mathbf{H}$ as the case of full CSI.

2.1.3 Quantization

The signals acquired by the antennas need to be quantized in order to be able to modify it digitally. During the quantization process is replaced each number with an approximation from a finite set of discrete values (levels). The quantized received signal is expressed as

$$\mathbf{y} = \mathbf{Q}(\mathbf{r}), \quad (3)$$

where \mathbf{r} is the received signal, shown in 1. The quantizer $\mathbf{Q}(\cdot)$ is defined as $Q(u) = \text{sign}(u)$, where $u \in \mathbb{R}$, and $\text{sign}(u)$ is the sign function that returns 1 if $u \geq 0$, and -1 if $u \leq 0$. For

a complex number $Z = a + jb$, $\mathbf{Q}(\cdot)$ is applied separately for the real and imaginary parts as $\mathbf{Q}(Z) = \text{sign}(a) + j\text{sign}(b)$. And, since \mathbf{r} is a vector, it is applied element-wise.

2.1.4 Symbol estimation

After the quantization process, the received symbols need to be estimated. A soft estimate of the transmitted symbols is obtained by processing the quantized received signal through the receive filter \mathbf{A} as follows

$$\tilde{x} = \mathbf{A}^H \mathbf{y}, \quad (4)$$

The receive filter \mathbf{A} needs to be chosen. The channel information needed to compute this filter is acquired through sending uplink pilots, as we have seen in section 2.1.2. To compute the receive filter \mathbf{A} we based on the LS $\hat{\mathbf{H}}$ -estimate shown in [2]. So, we compute the receive filter as follows

$$\mathbf{a}^i = \frac{\hat{\mathbf{h}}^i}{\|\hat{\mathbf{h}}^i\|^2}, \quad (5)$$

$$\mathbf{A}^H = \hat{\mathbf{H}}^\dagger = (\hat{\mathbf{H}}^H \hat{\mathbf{H}})^{-1} \hat{\mathbf{H}}^H. \quad (6)$$

In (5) it is shown the MRC (Maximal Ratio Combining) receive filter, where \mathbf{a}^i and $\hat{\mathbf{h}}^i$ are the i -th columns of \mathbf{A} and $\hat{\mathbf{H}}$, respectively. In (6) it is defined the ZF (Zero-Forcing) receive filter. The MRC receive filter maximizes the Signal-to-Noise Ratio (SNR) of the data symbol of a single user, ignoring the effect of multi-user interference. By contrast to MRC, the ZF receive filter focus his action in minimize the interferences among users symbols (Inter Symbol Interference, ISI) by forcing it to zero at the cost of noise enhancement.

Each receive filter has advantages and disadvantages. In case of using MRC receive filter are:

- Advantages: The signal processing is very simple since the BS just multiplies the received vector with the conjugate-transpose of the channel matrix \mathbf{H} , and then detects each stream separately. Furthermore, at low P_t , $SINR_{MRC,K} = P_t \|h_k\|^2$. This implies that at low SNR, MRC can achieve the same array gain as in the case of a single-user system.
- Disadvantages: Since MRC neglects the effect of multi-user interference, it performs poorly in interference-limited scenarios.

By contrast, in case of using ZF receive filter are:

- Advantages: The signal processing is simple and ZF works well in interference-limited scenarios. The SINR can be made as high as desired by increasing the transmit power.
- Disadvantages: Since ZF neglects the effect of noise, it works poorly under noise-limited scenarios. Furthermore, if the channel is not well-conditioned then the pseudo-inverse amplifies the noise significantly, and hence, the performance is very poor. Compared with MRC, ZF has a higher implementation complexity due to the computation of the pseudo-inverse of the channel matrix.

Once the receive filter is computed, we are able to estimate the receive symbol as it is shown in (4).

2.2 MmWave channel model

The channel at mmWave is different, compared with the presented in the subsection 2.1.2, which was a general fading channel. It is too much imprecise for modelling mmWaves and massive MIMO systems. The reason about it is different is because the propagation environment has a different effect on smaller wavelength signals. For example, diffraction tends to be lower due to the reduced Fresnel zone, scattering is higher due to the increased effective roughness of materials and penetration losses can be much larger, among other effects.

So, in this section, we explain how the mmWave channel can be modelled. We make use of a proposed channel model, which try to fit the effects produced by the mmWave on channels. That model introduces the phenomenon of clusters, which are composed by the rays of the users transmissions, and these can be modelled by a PDF (Probability Density Function). It also uses the named AOA (Angle of Arrival), which is the angle whereby the signal arrives to the BS. Finally, we show how the channel can be computed.

2.2.1 MmWave channel model description: The clustered channel model

We based the channel model of the system in the Saleh–Valenzuela model shown in [3]. That channel model is based on the user transmissions arriving from similar directions, besides delays and multiple scatterers around the receive base station are modelled as clusters. In this method, is associated a mean of AOA with each cluster, and the AOA of the rays within the same cluster are assumed to be distributed according to a certain PDF. Although the AOA is physically distributed over the 3-D space, it has been established through channel measurements that

most of the energy is localized over the azimuth directions. So, we assume the AOA to be distributed according to a certain Power Azimuth Spectrum (PAS).

Several distributions have been proposed to approximate the empirically observed PAS, but has been shown that the PAS is accurately modeled by the truncated Laplacian PDF, which is given by

$$\mathbf{P}_\phi(\phi) = \begin{cases} \frac{\beta}{\sqrt{2}\sigma_\phi} \cdot e^{-|\frac{\sqrt{2}\pi}{\sigma_\phi}|} & , \text{if } \phi \in [-\pi, \pi) \\ 0 & , \text{otherwise} \end{cases}, \quad (7)$$

where ϕ is the random variable describing the AOA offset with respect to the mean angle ϕ_0 , σ_ϕ is the standard deviation (rms) of the PAS, and $\beta = \frac{1}{1 - e^{-\frac{\sqrt{2}\pi}{\sigma_\phi}}}$ is the normalization factor needed to make the function integrate to one. The Laplace PDF described in 7 is shown in Figure 2.3.

Figure 2.3: Truncated Laplacian PDF with $\mu = 0$ and $\sigma^2 = 1$.

In Figure 2.3 is depicted the truncated Laplacian PDF considering mean $\mu = 0$ and standard deviation $\sigma = 1$. Figure 2.3 represents the angular offset values of the users rays, and therefore, the cluster angular spread, since the cluster is composed by the rays transmitted by a single user. The most probable value, as it is showed in the figure is 0, with a probability about 70%. The probability of an angle offset of 1° deg is about 17%. This would mean that the most probable case is that the ray has no spread and it is pointing to the centre of the cluster. But the rest

of the values are quite probable to happen too, so most of the rays will have a certain angular spread, different between them. In Figure 2.4 it is depicted a similar case, but this time using $\mu = 0$ and $\sigma^2 = 0.1$. As can be observed, in that case the 0 is more probable than before, which now is really close to 1, and hence the other values less probable. This means that the rays will have less angular spread, since the values different of zero are less probable than in the case of using $\sigma = 1$, and hence the dimensions of the cluster will be reduced. With this two Figures is demonstrate the influence of the sigma parameter in the Laplacian PDF, and therefore the angular spread of the rays and cluster. With a small variance σ , the distribution is narrowed, and in that case the angular spread of the rays would be lower, so most of the rays would point to the centre of the cluster.

Figure 2.4: Truncated Laplacian PDF with $\mu = 0$ and $\sigma^2 = 0.1$.

After we have the AOA offset of each ray, we need to define the possible cluster centre angle as $\phi \in [-60^\circ, 60^\circ]$. In other words, the clusters are uniformly distributed over 120° , as we show in Figure 2.5, because we consider a cell sectoring, instead of single omni-directional antenna array.

For example, considering a single user with two centre clusters (in -20° and 10°), two rays per cluster (with offsets -0.1° and $+0.15^\circ$ in the first cluster, and $+0.3^\circ$ and -0.2° in the second cluster). The resulting rays angular position would be $(-20^\circ - 0.1^\circ)$, $(-20^\circ + 0.15^\circ)$, $(10^\circ + 0.3^\circ)$ and $(10^\circ - 0.2^\circ)$, so the rays are situated in -20.1° , 19.85° , 10.3° and 9.8° . The clusters then goes from -20.1° , to 19.85° , and from 10.3° to 9.8° . This example is shown approximately in

Figure 2.5. In case of more users or larger number of rays per user, it follows the same procedure.

Figure 2.5: Example of clustered channel model with 1 user, 2 rays per user and 2 clusters.

Once we have defined the rays and clusters angular position, we are able to compute the channel matrix as

$$\mathbf{h}_k = \sqrt{\frac{M}{N_{cl}N_{ray}}} \sum_{l=1}^{N_{cl}} \sum_{i=1}^{N_{ray}} \alpha_{il} \mathbf{a}(\phi_{il}) \quad (8)$$

where \mathbf{h}_k is the channel vector for the user $k \in [1, 2, \dots, K]$. M is the number of receive antennas in the BS, N_{cl} is the number of clusters per user and N_{ray} is the number of rays per cluster. α_{il} is the Rayleigh channel coefficient, where $\alpha_{il} \in \mathcal{CN}(0, 1)$. And finally $\mathbf{a}(\phi_{il})$ is the steering vector, which represents the set of phase delays experienced by the BS antennas. It is defined (for $\lambda/2$ antenna separation) as $\mathbf{a}(\phi) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{M}} [1, e^{j\pi \sin \phi}, \dots, e^{j(M-1)\pi \sin \phi}]^T$.

By arranging the K channel vectors computed in 8 as columns in a matrix we finally obtain the expression for the channel matrix \mathbf{H} . So it can be written as follows

$$\mathbf{H} = [\mathbf{h}_1, \mathbf{h}_2, \dots, \mathbf{h}_K] \quad (9)$$

2.3 System model description with Beamforming

In this section, it is shown the system model in the case of use analog beamforming. The general idea is quite similar to the presented in section 2.3. But, in this occasion, we introduce the beamformer block before the quantization process, which let us discretise between users in reception, in order to obtain the transmitted symbols by a single user, instead of receive the transmissions of all the users added. So the beamforming process can be useful to cancel or attenuate signals from certain directions directions.

We make use of the mmWave model channel described in the previous section. We show the fundamentals of the beamformer, how it works, and we also comment the needed changes necessities into the system model shown previously to make working the analog beamforming.

2.3.1 Model description

Figure 2.6 shows the box diagram of the system. Just like it is shown, the only particularity with the box diagram shown in 2.1 is the block called Beamformer, located at the receiver before the quantizer. The K users transmits their data (vector \mathbf{x}), then the channel effect \mathbf{H} is applied and the AWGN noise is added. After that is applied the beamforming \mathbf{B} to the receive signal \mathbf{r} , just before quantize the signal (vector \mathbf{y}) as

$$\mathbf{y} = \mathbf{Q}(\mathbf{r}) = \mathbf{Q}(\mathbf{B}(\mathbf{H}\mathbf{x} + \mathbf{n})), \quad (10)$$

where \mathbf{B} is defined as

$$\mathbf{B} = \mathbf{D} \cdot \mathbf{R}^H. \quad (10)$$

And finally, it is applied the receive filter as we have done before, in order to estimate the received symbol. Note that now the dimensions of the signals after the beamformer are d , and since $d < M$, the system complexity and number of quantizers, and hence the energy consumption can be lower in comparison to a system without analog beamforming. Besides analog beamforming can also contribute to increase the system performance in terms of better SER and Mutual Information, as we will show in section 4.

We must notice that now, applying the beamforming, the computational complexity is far lower than it was without beamforming. Now, at the receiver, we have to deal with signals of dimension d , instead of M , and keeping in mind that $d < M$, the complexity and computational workload is lower. Besides, the number of quantizers needed in the system are reduced, since $d < M$, and it is used a quantizer for each antenna (M) or beam (d).

Figure 2.6: System model with beamforming.

2.3.2 Analog Beamforming

The beamformer block shown in 2.6 can be divided in two sub-blocks, the steering matrix $\mathbf{R} \in \mathbb{C}^{M \times d}$, where M is the number of antennas in the BS and d is the total number of beams, and the phase correction matrix \mathbf{D} , as it is shown in Figure 2.7.

The steering R matrix contain the d steering vectors, which contains the direction of arrival of the signal to each beam. and it is defined as

$$\mathbf{R} = [\mathbf{a}(\phi_1), \dots, \mathbf{a}(\phi_d)], \quad (11)$$

where (for $\lambda/2$ antenna separation) the steering vector \mathbf{a} , which is characterized by an equal phase shift between adjacent array elements can be calculated as

$$\mathbf{a}(\phi_i) = [1, e^{j\pi \sin \phi_i}, \dots, e^{j(M-1)\pi \sin \phi_i}]^T. \quad (12)$$

To compute $\mathbf{a}(\phi_i)$ we need to know ϕ_i in order to align the beams in the direction of the clusters to receive the signal correctly. We have aligned one of the beams of each cluster in the direction of the cluster centre ϕ_c , and the rest of them, separated a determined angle, adding a chosen $\pm \phi_{beamSeparation}$ to the cluster centre, which can be controlled in the parameters selection process. The only requirement for accomplish the presented beamforming implementation is that

Figure 2.7: System model with beamforming. Beamforming box is divided in the steering matrix R and correction matrix D .

we need to know the angular position of the cluster centres in advance. An example of this is shown in the Figure 2.8, which continues the example shown in the Figure 2.5. In that example it is considered the same number of clusters and rays positions, and it is considered 3 beams per cluster, this makes a total of 6 beams, since the total number of beams can be calculated as $d = 1 \text{ user} \cdot 2 \text{ clusters} \cdot 3 \text{ beams per cluster} = 6$. The beam in the middle of each cluster points to the cluster centre, and the two remaining points to the centre \pm a certain $\phi_{beamSeparation}$ (which must be chosen in advance), as we have mentioned before.

Figure 2.8: Example of 1 user, 2 cluster and 3 beams per cluster.

The phase correction matrix \mathbf{D} corrects phase shift induced by the effective channel, which is defined as

$$\mathbf{H}' = \mathbf{R}^H \mathbf{H}, \quad (13)$$

where \mathbf{H} is the mmWave channel (full CSI or estimated). So the effective channel is defined by the real channel between the single-antenna users and the antennas in the BS, and the steering matrix \mathbf{R} . It can be split as

$$\mathbf{H}' = [\mathbf{h}'_1, \mathbf{h}'_2, \dots, \mathbf{h}'_d]^T. \quad (14)$$

To compute \mathbf{D} we must find the corresponding phase correction angle β_i , which contains the

phase correction angles for each one of the beams. So using equation (14) we can obtain the angle β_i as

$$\beta_i = \angle(\mathbf{h}'_i(ind)), \quad (15)$$

where \angle is the angle function that returns the phase angles for the element ind of complex array. The ind value can be obtained as

$$[\sim, ind] = \max(\text{abs}(\mathbf{h}'_i)). \quad (16)$$

Finally we compute the phase correction matrix \mathbf{D} as

$$\mathbf{D} = \begin{bmatrix} e^{-j\beta_1} & & \\ & \ddots & \\ & & e^{-j\beta_d} \end{bmatrix} \quad (17)$$

where we obtain a diagonal matrix that contains the phase correction angle in the diagonal and the rest are zero values. Note that the arguments of the exponentials are negative, in order to reverse the phase shift induced by the effective channel.

3 Performance metrics

In this section are shown the methods used to compute the chosen performance metrics, the Symbol Error Rate, and the Mutual Information between the sent and the estimated symbols. We show how they can be calculated by two ways, numerically and analytically.

In the case where the performance metrics are evaluated numerically, $p(\hat{x}_k|x_k, \mathbf{H})$ is estimated by Monte Carlo simulations with many realizations of the transmit vector \mathbf{x} and the channel noise vector \mathbf{n} , which is shown in the section 3.1. In the section 3.2 it is calculated analytically by the closed-form derivation of the symbol estimate PMF (Probability Mass Function), and in this section is described the procedure to obtain it. Finally, it is shown a comparison between the numerical and analytical performance metrics evaluation, in order to show the accuracy of the analytical method compared with the numerical. The performance metrics analysis shown in this section is obtained from [2].

3.1 Monte Carlo simulations

3.1.1 Symbol Error Rate

The analysis of SER by means of Monte Carlo simulations is really simple. We only need to do several realizations of the transmit vector \mathbf{x} and the AWGN channel noise vector \mathbf{n} . We have chosen 10^5 realizations in order to obtain the results as accurate as we need. In each realization we must run the entire system, which transmits, receive and estimate the symbols. Then we must compute the probability of error as

$$SER = p(\hat{x}_k \neq x_k), \quad (18)$$

where $p(\hat{x}_k \neq x_k)$ is the probability that the QPSK symbol estimated \hat{x}_k at the receiver is different from the transmitted QPSK symbol x_k by the user. Once we have computed the probability of error in each realization, we must average it over the total number of realizations, and finally, we obtain the SER of the system transmission.

3.1.2 Mutual Information

The Mutual Information associated with the discrete channel between x_k and \hat{x}_k is calculated as

$$I(x_k; \hat{x}_k) = E_H \left[\sum_{x_k, \hat{x}_k} p(\hat{x}_k|x_k, \mathbf{H})p(x_k) \log_2 \frac{p(\hat{x}_k|x_k, \mathbf{H})}{p(\hat{x}_k|\mathbf{H})} \right], \quad (19)$$

where $p(\hat{x}_k|x_k, \mathbf{H})$ is the PMF(Probability Mass Function) of \hat{x}_k given x_k and \mathbf{H} , $p(x_k)$ is the PMF of a QPSK constellation with uniformly distributed symbols, and $p(\hat{x}_k|\mathbf{H}) = \sum_{x_k} p(\hat{x}_k|x_k, \mathbf{H})p(x_k)$.

The probability $p(x_k)$ is equal to 0.25, since the QPSK modulation has 4 symbols and we consider it with the same probability. So, we need to compute the transition probabilities $p(\hat{x}_k|x_k, \mathbf{H})$.

In order to compute it, we need to do many realizations of the symbol and noise vectors by each channel realization. We have chosen 10^2 channel matrix realizations, and for each channel realization, 10^2 random symbol and noise vectors realizations. The number of Monte Carlo simulations have been chosen in order to satisfy the results accuracy that we need.

So, in order to obtain the probabilities $p(\hat{x}_k|x_k, \mathbf{H})$, we need to count how many times we estimate the received symbol mistakenly in the total amount of simulations, and how many times we compute each one of the possible symbols. That means that if we sent $\frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}(1 + j)$, we need to count how many times we estimate the symbol mistakenly as $\frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}(1 - j)$, $\frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}(-1 - j)$ or $\frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}(-1 + j)$ in the total amount of simulations. Doing that we obtain 4 probabilities, one for each symbol estimation. We should compute it for the 16 possible combinations of symbols transmitted and received, but since once is done for one of the symbols, the others can be obtained by symmetry. The only thing we need to keep in mind is that in equation 19 we need to multiply it by a factor of 4, since we only have the probabilities for one of the symbols. Once we have the probabilities $p(\hat{x}_k|x_k, \mathbf{H})$ we can compute the mutual information as we have shown in equation (19).

3.2 Analytical approach

The analytical approach is a bit more complicated than the numerical. Firstly, we explain the process of the analytical approach in case of no analog beamforming applied, and then we relate it to the analog beamforming case.

In first place, we need to define $f(\tilde{x}_k|x_k, \mathbf{H})$, which is the PDF of \tilde{x}_k given x_k and \mathbf{H} . Now we need to find this PDF of \tilde{x} , which must fit well with the real probability distribution. In order to do that, it is used the Cramer's central limit theorem, which states that the sum $\sum_{i=1}^L u_i$ of a large number of independent random variables is approximately complex Gaussian if the following conditions are satisfied:

1. Every component u_i has a zero mean value.
2. Every component u_i has a finite variance $a_i^2 = E [|u_i|^2]$.
3. $\frac{a_i}{S_L} \xrightarrow{L \rightarrow \infty} 0$ and $S_L \xrightarrow{L \rightarrow \infty} \infty$, where $S_L = \sum_{i=1}^L a_i^2$.

Therefore, applying the Cramer's central limit theorem, we obtain that:

$$\tilde{x}_k|x_k, \mathbf{H} \xrightarrow{M \rightarrow \infty} \mathcal{CN} \left(\sum_{i=1}^M \mu_i, \sum_{i=1}^M \sigma_i^2 \right), \quad (20)$$

where μ_i is the mean, and σ_i^2 is the variance. Both are computed for the antenna i as

$$\mu_i = \frac{h_{ik}^*}{\|h_k\|^2} \sum_{c=1}^4 P_{ic} S_c, \quad (21)$$

and

$$\sigma_i^2 = \frac{|h_{ik}|^2}{\|h_k\|^4} \left(2 - \left| \sum_{c=1}^4 P_{ic} S_c \right|^2 \right), \quad (22)$$

where $\frac{h_{ik}^*}{\|h_k\|^2}$ and $\frac{|h_{ik}|^2}{\|h_k\|^4}$ are the MRC receive filter $\mathbf{A}^{\mathbf{H}}$ and \mathbf{A}^2 , respectively, shown in equation (5), S_c are the possible quantized symbols: $S_1 = 1 + j$, $S_2 = 1 - j$, $S_3 = -1 - j$ and $S_4 = -1 + j$. And P_{ic} are the error probabilities of quantize a determined y , knowing that the user has sent a determined symbol x_k (in the case that is showed, we have choose $x_k = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} + j \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}$) in each antenna. This P_{ic} error probabilities can be calculated using the complementary error function as

$$\begin{aligned} P_{i1} &= \text{Prob}(y_i = 1 + j | x_k = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}(1 + j), \mathbf{H}) = \\ &= \frac{1}{2} \text{erfc} \left(-\frac{\sqrt{P_t} \text{Re}(h_{ik} x_k)}{\sqrt{\sigma_N^2 + (\sigma^I)^2}} \right) \cdot \frac{1}{2} \text{erfc} \left(-\frac{\sqrt{P_t} \text{Im}(h_{ik} x_k)}{\sqrt{\sigma_N^2 + (\sigma^I)^2}} \right), \end{aligned} \quad (23)$$

$$\begin{aligned}
P_{i1} &= \text{Prob}(y_i = 1 - j | x_k = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}(1 + 1j), \mathbf{H}) = \\
&= \frac{1}{2} \text{erfc} \left(-\frac{\sqrt{P_t} \text{Re}(h_{ik}x_k)}{\sqrt{\sigma_N^2 + (\sigma^I)^2}} \right) \cdot \left(1 - \frac{1}{2} \text{erfc} \left(-\frac{\sqrt{P_t} \text{Im}(h_{ik}x_k)}{\sqrt{\sigma_N^2 + (\sigma^I)^2}} \right) \right), \tag{24}
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
P_{i1} &= \text{Prob}(y_i = -1 - j | x_k = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}(1 + 1j), \mathbf{H}) = \\
&= \left(1 - \frac{1}{2} \text{erfc} \left(-\frac{\sqrt{P_t} \text{Re}(h_{ik}x_k)}{\sqrt{\sigma_N^2 + (\sigma^I)^2}} \right) \right) \cdot \left(1 - \frac{1}{2} \text{erfc} \left(-\frac{\sqrt{P_t} \text{Im}(h_{ik}x_k)}{\sqrt{\sigma_N^2 + (\sigma^I)^2}} \right) \right), \tag{25}
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
P_{i1} &= \text{Prob}(y_i = -1 + j | x_k = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}(1 + 1j), \mathbf{H}) = \\
&= \left(1 - \frac{1}{2} \text{erfc} \left(-\frac{\sqrt{P_t} \text{Re}(h_{ik}x_k)}{\sqrt{\sigma_N^2 + (\sigma^I)^2}} \right) \right) \cdot \frac{1}{2} \text{erfc} \left(-\frac{\sqrt{P_t} \text{Im}(h_{ik}x_k)}{\sqrt{\sigma_N^2 + (\sigma^I)^2}} \right), \tag{26}
\end{aligned}$$

where σ_N^2 is the AWGN noise power and $(\sigma^I)^2 = P_t \sum_{j=1, j \neq k}^K |h_{ij}|^2$, which represents the interference provoked by the users among them. That is the reason because in the summation of $(\sigma^I)^2$, we use $j \neq k$, because the user k can not be considered interference for himself, only must be considered interference the rest of them.

Notice that we are only considering a single symbol in the computation of P_{ic} , in that case $x_k = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} + j \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}$. But the process would be similar for other possible values of x_k .

Once that $f(\tilde{x}_k | x_k, \mathbf{H})$ is known, it gives us the distribution of \tilde{x}_k given x_k and \mathbf{H} . So the transition probabilities $p(\hat{x}_k | x_k, \mathbf{H})$ required to compute the SER and the Mutual Information as we will see in the following sections, it can be calculated either numerically or using complementary error functions. If nothing else is mentioned, the probabilities $p(\hat{x}_k | x_k, \mathbf{H})$ are obtained by complementary error functions as follows

$$P1 = \frac{1}{2} \text{erfc} \left(-\frac{\text{Re}(\mu)}{\sqrt{\sigma^2}} \right) \cdot \frac{1}{2} \text{erfc} \left(-\frac{\text{Re}(\mu)}{\sqrt{\sigma^2}} \right), \tag{27}$$

$$P2 = \frac{1}{2} \text{erfc} \left(-\frac{\text{Re}(\mu)}{\sqrt{\sigma^2}} \right) \cdot \left(1 - \frac{1}{2} \text{erfc} \left(-\frac{\text{Re}(\mu)}{\sqrt{\sigma^2}} \right) \right), \tag{28}$$

$$P3 = \left(1 - \frac{1}{2} \operatorname{erfc} \left(-\frac{\operatorname{Re}(\mu)}{\sqrt{\sigma^2}}\right)\right) \cdot \left(1 - \frac{1}{2} \operatorname{erfc} \left(-\frac{\operatorname{Re}(\mu)}{\sqrt{\sigma^2}}\right)\right), \quad (29)$$

$$P4 = \left(1 - \frac{1}{2} \operatorname{erfc} \left(-\frac{\operatorname{Re}(\mu)}{\sqrt{\sigma^2}}\right)\right) \cdot \frac{1}{2} \operatorname{erfc} \left(-\frac{\operatorname{Re}(\mu)}{\sqrt{\sigma^2}}\right), \quad (30)$$

where μ and σ^2 are from equation (20) and computed in equations (21) and (22).

Note that the process of compute the probabilities of error by complementary error functions should be done for all the possible cases (4 cases for each x_k , a total of 16), since we are evaluating the error probability of each x_k . But in fact, by computing the first four cases (for a determined x_k) showed in (27), (28), (29) and (30) we can obtain the rest of them by symmetry, so it is only needed to compute it for a single x_k . The only difference of doing that is when we compute the SER in (31) (or the mutual information in (??)), we have to multiply it by a factor of 4, because we have only calculated 4 cases instead of 16. In fact, it's the same that happened in the computation of the Mutual Information by Monte Carlo simulations.

Once we have the four error probability calculated in (27)-(30), we are able to compute the SER and Mutual Information as it is shown in the following sections.

To finish, we must mention that in the case of the analog beamforming is applied, we have to keep in mind that we don't have M antennas, because instead of that, we have d beams. So P_{ic} , μ_i and σ_i^2 instead of calculate it for each antenna, it is calculated for each beam.

3.2.1 Symbol Error Rate

The SER can be easily calculated by means of the analytic approach as

$$SER = E_H \left[\sum_{x_k} \sum_{\hat{x}_k \neq x_k} p(\hat{x}_k | x_k, \mathbf{H}) p(x_k) \right], \quad (31)$$

where $p(\hat{x}_k | x_k, \mathbf{H})$ is the PMF of \hat{x}_k given x_k and \mathbf{H} , and $p(x_k)$ is the PMF of a QPSK constellation with uniformly distributed symbols, which means equal to 0.25. Only $p(\hat{x}_k | x_k, \mathbf{H})$ needs to be calculated. And as we have shown previously, it can be done using equations (27)-(30). The equation (31) needs to be multiplied by a factor of 4, since we have only calculated the probabilities for a single symbol, instead of all the possible symbols, as we have already mentioned.

3.2.2 Mutual Information

To compute the Mutual Information analytically we need to use equation (19). The procedure to obtain the transition probabilities $p(\hat{x}_k|x_k, \mathbf{H})$ is the same than in the computation of the SER, which is shown in equations (27)-(30). We need to apply also the factor of 4, by the reasons that we have already mentioned.

3.3 Numerical and analytical methods comparison

In this section, we compare the two methods described above in order to verify the analytical analysis and to show the accuracy of it.

In Figures 3.1 and 3.2 we show the SER and Mutual Information, respectively, computed numerically by Monte Carlo simulations, as it is showed in section 3.1, and computed by the analytical analysis, shown in section 3.2.

As it can be observed in Figures 3.1 and 3.2, both methods are similar, since both curves are almost identical at any SNR. If we focus the attention on the SER, we could say that the analytical approach is more accurate at low SNR, but still accurate enough at high SNR. However, if we focus the attention on the Mutual Information, we observe as the analytical approach is equally valid at any SNR.

With this brief comparison we confirm that both methods are equally valid, and we prove that the analytical approach is accurate enough. So both methods may be exchangeable between them.

Figure 3.1: SER per user versus SNR considering $M = 400$ and $K = 20$, and the MRC filter with full CSI. Monte Carlo symbol and noise vectors simulation results are compared with the analytical results based on 20 and 31.

Figure 3.2: Mutual Information per user versus SNR considering $M = 400$ and $K = 20$, and the MRC filter with full CSI. Monte Carlo symbol and noise vectors simulation results are compared with the analytical results based on 20 and 19.

4 Results

In this section are shown the obtained results of the project. It is divided in two blocks. In the first block are shown the results about the SER, and in the second block are shown the results about the Mutual Information. In both cases are shown the results without applying analog beamforming and applying it, and then are both compared. We have tested some parameter values of the system, such as the number of users or the number of BS antennas, in order to show the different performances provoked by change It. We also show the results for using different beamforming parameters, such as the number of clusters, the number of rays per cluster, the number of beams per cluster or the angular spread of the beams, among other. We also show the importance of the training pilot length sequence in the channel estimation process by comparing different lengths of it.

It is also showed the differences in the performance provoked by using mmWaves, by comparing the performance of the system by using the fading channel model and the mmWave channel model described in 2.2. For the simulations using the mmWave channel model, we have considered 2 clusters and 10 rays per cluster. These are average values found in recent experimental mmWaves channel measurements [7].

4.1 Symbol Error Rate

4.1.1 SER with no analog beamforming applied

In this section are depicted the results of SER without analog beamforming applied. In Figures 4.1 and 4.2 are depicted the SER per user versus the SNR computed by means of Monte Carlo Simulations. The objective of the graphs is to show how the length of the training sequences N affects the performance, focusing the attention on the MRC and the ZF receivers. As we have said in section 2.1.2, we consider six values of N , divided in two blocks: $50K$, $10K$, $5K$, where K is the number of users, and $50M$, $10M$ and $5M$, where M is the number of BS antennas. In the case of Figures 4.1 and 4.2, we consider 20 users, so the pilot training lengths are, respectively, 1000, 200 and 100 symbols for Figure 4.1, and 400 antennas, so the pilot training lengths are

20000, 4000 and 2000 symbols, for Figure 4.2.

As we can observe from Figure 4.1, for values at very low SNR, such as -20 dB, there are not considerably greater differences between the MRC and the ZF filters considering the same pilot training length. So, if we compare the values of SER between MRC and ZF using the same length of training sequence at low SNR, both are quite similar. The differences increase as the SNR gets greater. For example, setting the reference SER to 10^{-3} , the ZF filter needs a SNR around -12 dB (for the cases Full CSI and training length of $50k$), -10 dB (for a training length of $10k$) and -8 dB (for a training length of $5k$). However, the MRC filter needs to accomplish the same SER conditions, a SNR around -6 dB, -4 dB and 0 dB, respectively, which is practically in most of the cases, to double the SNR in logarithmic scale. Notice that the Full CSI and $N = 50k$ cases, have both similar performance. So, as a summary, we could say that to achieve the same performance as the full CSI case, we have to use training sequence as long as we can. This could be possible in a scenario where the environment, and hence the channel, does not vary really fast. That is because the more large is the training sequence, better is the channel estimation, but more time it takes to estimate it. So if the channel changes really fast, there is not enough time to estimate it reliably, because once it is estimated, the channel has changed.

Figure 4.1: SER per user versus SNR for $M=400$ and $K=20$. The ZF and MRC filters are considered for both the cases of perfect and imperfect CSI. The training sequence length depends on the number of users K . The fading channel model has been used.

In Figure 4.2 we show a similar case of the shown in 4.1, but this time the training length of the sequences are: $50M$, $10M$ and $5M$. Therefore, are larger, since $K \ll M$. In this Figure is confirmed what we have said. If the training length is long enough, the performance estimating the channel is approximately the full CSI. But, as we have said, it is only realizable in scenarios where there are not too much changes, impossible for example in a city, where the channel changes very fast due above all the people and vehicles in constant movement.

Figure 4.2: SER per user versus SNR for $M=400$ and $K=20$. The ZF and MRC filters are considered for both the cases of perfect and imperfect CSI. The training sequence length depends on the number of antennas M . The fading channel model has been used.

Finally, in Figure 4.3 is depicted the SER per user versus the SNR computed by means of Monte Carlo Simulations using 20 single antenna users, 400 BS antennas, 2 clusters and 10 rays per cluster. But, this time the results have been computed using the mmWave channel model described in section 2.2, instead of using the fading channel model. This is done in order to show the effects provoked in the performance of the system by using mmWaves. As can be observed comparing Figures 4.1 and 4.3, the performance of the system is slightly lower using the ZF filter, although still close to the fading channel, and rather lower using the MRC filter. If we focus on the ZF filter, now the Full CSI and the $N = 50k$ cases need about -11 dB to accomplish the SER of 10^{-3} , and using the fading channel it needed about -12 dB. The $N = 10k$ and $N = 5k$ now needs about -8 dB and -5 dB, respectively, instead of -10 dB and -8 dB, respectively. On the contrary, If we focus on the MRC filter, the minimum SER is about 0.02 at 0 dB of SNR, which compared with the fading channel case, is a huge deterioration of the performance.

The mmWave channel model produces a deterioration of the SNR in 1-2 dB, at $\text{SER}=10^{-3}$, in the ZF receive filter. And in the MRC produces a huge deterioration, now the minimum SER at 0 dB is about 10^{-2} . So the MRC filter is more affected by using mmWaves than the ZF.

We have also depicted in Figures 4.4 and 4.5 the SER per user versus the SNR for two more different cases, which we will use to compare the system with and without beamforming in the next section. In the first case we have chosen 10 single-antenna users and 200 BS antennas, In the second we have selected 5 single-antenna users and 100 BS antennas. The number of clusters and rays per clusters have been maintained to 2 and 10, respectively.

Both cases will be analysed in detail in the following section, but, as can be observed easily, the performance of the system is strictly related to the number of users and BS antennas into

Figure 4.3: SER per user versus SNR for $M=400$ and $K=20$. The ZF and MRC filters are considered for both the cases of perfect and imperfect CSI. The training sequence length depends on the number of antennas K . The mmWave channel model has been used with 2 clusters per user and 10 rays per cluster.

Figure 4.4: SER per user versus SNR for $M=200$ and $K=10$. The ZF and MRC filters are considered for both the cases of perfect and imperfect CSI. The training sequence length depends on the number of antennas K . The mmWave channel model has been used with 2 clusters per user and 10 rays per cluster.

Figure 4.5: SER per user versus SNR for $M=100$ and $K=5$. The ZF and MRC filters are considered for both the cases of perfect and imperfect CSI. The training sequence length depends on the number of antennas K . The mmWave channel model has been used with 2 clusters per user and 10 rays per cluster.

the system. So, as larger is the number of BS antennas, better is the performance of SER. Just as lower is the number of single-antenna users, better is the performance of SER.

4.1.2 SER with analog beamforming applied

In this section are depicted the results of the system for analog beamforming applied and diverse parameters configurations. This results are then compared with the showed in the previous section, which was with no beamforming applied. This is done in order to evaluate the performance of SER and measure if there is an improvement by using analog beamforming. The mmWave channel model has been used to obtain the results.

In Figure 4.6 is depicted the SER using 10 single-antenna users and 200 antennas in the BS. Besides it is considered 2 clusters per user and 10 rays per cluster, 6 beams per cluster and a cluster beam separation of 0.4° deg. In Figure 4.4 is depicted the SER of the system considering the same system parameters, but without applying the beamforming. If we compare Figures 4.6 and 4.4 we observe that the performance of the system with beamforming applied in that case is quite poor. For example, the SER values at 0 dB using beamforming are about 10^{-1} and 10^{-2} approximately, for MRC and ZF, respectively, while without beamforming are between 10^{-4} and 10^{-5} for the ZF, and 10^{-2} for the MRC. So using this configuration in the system is evident that there are not too much improvement in the performance of the system, quite the opposite. So in this particular case with this amount of users and BS antennas in the beamforming do not provide any improvement at all. The advantage of using beamforming in this situation would be regarding to the reduction of the system dimensionality and number of quantizers, and hence

the power consumption.

Figure 4.6: SER per user versus SNR for $M=200$ and $K=10$. It is considered 2 cluster per user, 10 rays per cluster, 6 beam per cluster, beam separation 0.4° deg and Laplacian PDF standard deviation 0.25. The ZF and MRC filters are considered for both the cases of perfect and imperfect CSI.

In Figure 4.7 is depicted the SER using 5 single-antenna users and 100 antennas in the BS. Besides is considered 2 clusters per user and 10 rays per cluster, 5 beams per cluster and a cluster beam separation of 0.1° deg. In Figure 4.8 is depicted the SER using the same parameters than in Figure 4.7, but this time doubling the beams per cluster, in order to show the effect provoked by doubling it. In Figure 4.5 is depicted the SER of the system without applying beamforming in order to be able to compare the system under the same conditions.

In Figure 4.7 we can observe that the SER is about 10^{-2} and 0.05 for the ZF, and MRC filters respectively, at 0 dB of SNR. In Figure 4.8, which is the other beamforming case, we can see that we need a SNR between -4 dB and -2 dB to obtain a SER of 10^{-3} in the ZF receive filter case, and the MRC filter minimum SER is about 0.003. So by doubling the number of beams we obtain a substantial performance improvement, which is about an order on magnitude. However, in Figure 4.5, the SER under the same conditions is about 10^{-3} and 10^{-4} , and 10^{-2} , for the ZF and MRC filters, respectively. So at first sight there is not a considerable improvement by using beamforming.

In Figure 4.9 is depicted a comparison between the system parameters shown in Figures 4.7, 4.8 and 4.5 in order to compare the three cases more easily in the same Figure, but only considering the channel estimation case $N = 50K$. In this Figure we can easily observe that using beamforming with 5 beams per cluster don't provoke any improvement in terms of SER, as we suspect. However, doubling the beams per cluster to 10, we appreciate that using or not using the beamforming produces similar results. That could seem a positive result, but using 10

Figure 4.7: SER per user versus SNR for $M=100$ and $K=5$. It is considered 2 cluster per user, 10 rays per cluster, 5 beam per cluster, beam separation 0.1° deg and Laplacian PDF standard deviation 0.25. The ZF and MRC filters are considered for both the cases of perfect and imperfect CSI.

Figure 4.8: SER per user versus SNR for $M=100$ and $K=5$. It is considered 2 cluster per user, 10 rays per cluster, 10 beam per cluster, beam separation 0.1° deg and Laplacian PDF standard deviation 0.25. The ZF and MRC filters are considered for both the cases of perfect and imperfect CSI.

beams per cluster means that the total number of beams d is 100 (since $d = 10 \text{ beams} \cdot 2 \text{ users} \cdot 10 \text{ beams per user} = 100$), which is equal to the number of antennas M . So in this particular case considering only the pilot training length of $N = 50K$ we obtain similar results, but using the same number of quantizers and hence power consumption, besides the beamforming implies put in computational complexities that maybe are not required.

Then in Figure 4.10 is depicted a complete comparison between the case with 10 beams per cluster showed in 4.8, and the case without beamforming showed in 4.5. In the superior part of Figure 4.10 are depicted only the results for the MRC receive filter, and in the inferior part are depicted only for the ZF receive filter, in order to be able to see the differences more clearly. If we focus on the MRC comparison, we observe that from about -4 dB, the performance of the system with beamforming is better than the non beamforming. This improvement is not too much noticeable, but there is an improvement. However, at low SNR the performance of using beamforming is slightly lower than without using it. If we focus on the ZF comparison, we observe that the beamforming produces a considerable improvement of the performance, above all from -5 dB. For the training length sequence $N = 5K$, both curves are equivalent until -10 dB, where the performance of the beamforming case grows faster than the non beamforming. The same happens with the rest of training length and the full CSI, but at -9 dB for the training length sequence $N = 10K$, and -3 dB for the training length sequence $N = 50K$ and full CSI cases. If we focus on the performance for example at 0 dB, we can easily see that the beamforming case produces a remarkable improvement, above all in the training length sequence $N = 5K$, which improves almost an order of magnitude, from $2.5 \cdot 10^{-3}$ to 10^{-4} . Besides at high SNR we can obtain an improvement of almost 2 dB using $N = 50K$ and ZF receiver, and even more for the rest of training sequence lengths. The rest of the cases also improve by applying the analog beamforming, reaching a maximum SER performance of about $3 \cdot 10^{-5}$ for the training length sequence $N = 50K$ and about $2 \cdot 10^{-5}$ for the full CSI. But as we have already said, this case with 10 beams per cluster do not permit us to obtain any benefit about the power consumption, since we are using the same number of quantizers, besides we are making more complex the system. The only benefit is the improvement of the SER performance from a certain SNR. But we must keep in mind that by improving the performance, even if it is only at high SNR, we can reduce the power consumption of the users transmitter devices, which can be traduced in better battery life of the user terminals.

So, in order to obtain a system with both benefits, the reduction of the power consumption and the improvement of the system performance, we have chosen the same parameters described above, but reducing the number of beams per cluster from 10 to 8. With this, we obtain a total number of beams d of 80 (since $d = 8 \text{ beams} \cdot 5 \text{ users} \cdot 2 \text{ clusters per user} = 80$), which is considerably lower than the number of antennas M , which is 100. In Figure 4.11 is depicted a detailed comparison between the beamforming and without beamforming cases for both the ZF and MRC receive filters. If we focus on the MRC comparison, we observe that the case without

Figure 4.9: SER per user versus SNR for $M=100$ and $K=5$. It is considered 3 different cases, 2 with beamforming and another without it. We also consider 2 cluster per user, 10 rays per cluster, 5 or 10 beam per cluster, beam separation 1° deg and Laplacian PDF standard deviation 0.25. The ZF and MRC filters are considered for imperfect CSI with $N = 50K$ pilot training length.

beamforming has a better performance until about -2 dB, where the beamforming case obtain slightly better results. As can be observed, at 0 dB of SNR all the considered cases has a SER of about 10^{-2} . If we focus on the ZF comparison, we observe that without beamforming the system has a better performance until about -1 dB, a similar result of the obtained in the MRC receive filter. From -1 dB the performance of the beamforming system is slightly better, even though very similar in both cases. So in all the considered cases using the ZF filter at 0 dB we obtain a SER between 10^{-3} and 10^{-4} , which is very similar to the system without beamforming. So using 8 beams per cluster and the parameters described above is observed as the system has the same performance, but the dimensionality and number of quantizers of the system has been reduced from 100 to 80, and hence the power consumption.

In Figure 4.12 is depicted a detailed comparison between using and not using the phase correction matrix D before quantization, and the effects of it in the performance of SER. By not using the phase correction matrix implies that the constellation of the QPSK modulated signal before the quantizer is rotated and no effort is put in the objective to shift the constellation points to the correct quadrant centres. The chosen system system parameters are: 5 single-antenna users, 100 BS antennas, 2 clusters and 10 rays per cluster and 8 beams with a cluster beam separation of 0.1° deg. As can be observed in Figure 4.12, the performance of the system at low SNR is similar using and not using the phase correction matrix. But from approximately -15 dB, if we don't use the phase correction matrix, the SER performance increase their distance by getting worse, until at 0 dB it is enormously deteriorated and dissimilar. This happens using any receive filter, the MRC or the ZF. That is because we are not correcting at all the phase

Figure 4.10: SER per user versus SNR for $M=100$ and $K=5$. It is considered the case with beamforming and 10 beams and without beamforming. The MRC (above) and ZF (below) filters are considered for both the cases of perfect and imperfect CSI.

Figure 4.11: SER per user versus SNR for $M=100$ and $K=5$. It is considered the system with beamforming and 8 beams and without beamforming. The MRC (top) and ZF (bottom) filters are considered for both the cases of perfect and imperfect CSI.

shift induced by the effective channel, and hence it provoke us more errors at reception than usual. If we focus on the MRC results, the fact of not use the phase matrix correction deteriorate the SER about an order of magnitude. With phase correction matrix we obtain a SER about 10^{-2} and without use it we obtain a SER about 10^{-1} , depending on the selected pilot training length, but quite similar for all of them. However, the ZF results show as the system is more dependant on the pilot training sequence length. For lower sequence lengths, the differences are smaller than for the bigger ones.

Figure 4.12: SER per user versus SNR for $M=100$ and $K=5$. It is considered the case with beamforming and 8 beams with and without apply the phase correction matrix D . The MRC (top) and ZF (bottom) filters are considered for both the cases of perfect and imperfect CSI.

Lastly, to end this section, we show the real effects on the SER performance provoked by increasing the Laplacian PDF standard deviation. In Figure 4.13 is depicted the SER versus the SNR for 5 single-antenna users, 100 BS antennas, 2 clusters per user and 10 rays per cluster, 8

beams per cluster, 0.1° deg of separation between beams and two different values of Laplacian standard deviation, 1 and 0.25. As it is shown in Figures 2.3 and 2.4 in section 2.2.1, by using bigger values of standard deviation in the Laplacian PDF, the PDF gets wider, and hence the rays per cluster are more scattered, which means that the size of the clusters are bigger as we have already explained in section 2.2.1. The result of it, as can be seen, is that the SER of the system is affected by getting worse performance. With bigger values of standard deviation, the clusters are more spread, as we have already said, and hence the beams of the beamforming should be also more spread, in order to receive the maximum quantity of rays possible. But, as the beams angular separation does not change, we are not able to receive all the rays from the clusters, and hence the performance is worse. At low SNR the SER performance is quite similar for both receive filters and Laplacian standard deviations, comparing it between the same training length sequence. If we focus the attention on the MRC filter, we observe as the SER performance is almost a straight line using a standard deviation of 1, which means that the SER value at 0 dB of SNR is about 0.2 for all the pilot training length, while using a standard deviation of 0.25, we obtain a SER between 0.01 and 0.0036, depending on the pilot training length considered, which is considerably lower. Focusing the attention on the ZF receive filter we observe that for the standard deviation of 1, the results are quite similar of the shown in the MRC filter, obtaining a SER about 0.2. However, the performances of both systems for the ZF are more dissimilar. Using the standard deviation of 0.25, we obtain a SER between 10^{-3} and 10^{-4} , which shows as the SER performance improves incredibly by reducing the standard deviation.

Figure 4.13: SER per user versus SNR for $M=100$ and $K=5$. It is considered the case with beamforming and 8 beams using two different Laplace PDF standard deviation, $\sigma = 0.1$ and $\sigma = 1$. The MRC (top) and ZF (bottom) filters are considered for both the cases of perfect and imperfect CSI.

4.2 Mutual Information

4.2.1 Mutual Information with no analog beamforming applied

In this section are depicted the results of Mutual information without analog beamforming applied. In Figure 4.14 is depicted the Mutual Information per user versus the SNR, computed by means of Monte Carlo simulations for 20 single antenna users and 400 BS antennas. This Figure is analogous to Figure 4.1, and shows how the length of the training sequences N affects the performance of the Mutual Information, focusing the attention on the MRC and the ZF receivers.

Analysing the Figure 4.14, we could say that the results, overall, are equivalent to the presented in Figure 4.1. This means that, there are not considerably greater differences between the MRC and ZF filters, considering the same pilot training length. Although, the ZF receive filter shows a slightly better performance than the MRC considering the same SNR in all the training length cases taken into account.

If we focus on the values at low SNR, the differences are minimum between the ZF and MRC filters considering the same pilot length, above all with the pilot training sequence length $N = 10K$ and $N = 5K$. But when the SNR increases the differences get bigger, approximately in the same manner as we have seen in Figure 4.1. When the SNR is sufficiently high (for example from 0 dB to 10 dB), all the considered cases show the maximum available capacity of a QPSK modulation, which is 2 (since it is determined by the number of bits used by the QPSK modulation for each symbol, which is 2 bits per symbol).

If we focus on the ZF receive filter, we observe that it needs a minimum SNR of -10 dB approximately, to reach the maximum capacity for all the training length sequences. For its part, the MRC needs a minimum SNR of -5 dB, which is a SNR almost 3 times better in lineal scale.

Figure 4.15 is analogous with Figure 4.2. Although this time it represents the mutual information instead of the SER. Analysing it, we could get similar conclusions. If the training length is long enough, the performance estimating the channel is approximately the full CSI. And hence the performance results are as if we knew the CSI of the channel. But unfortunately this is only realizable in scenarios where the environment, and hence the channel, does not vary really fast.

In Figure 4.16 is depicted the mutual information versus the SNR, but this time, using the mmWave channel model. It has been used 20 single-antenna users and 400 BS antennas, and 2 clusters per user and 10 rays per cluster. The purpose of this Figure is to show the effects provoked by using mmWave in the mutual information performance, focusing the attention in

Figure 4.14: Mutual Information versus SNR for $M=400$ and $K=20$. The ZF and MRC filters are considered for both the cases of perfect and imperfect CSI. The training sequence length depends on the number of users K . The fading channel model has been used.

Figure 4.15: Mutual Information versus SNR for $M=400$ and $K=20$. The ZF and MRC filters are considered for both the cases of perfect and imperfect CSI. The training sequence length depends on the number of antennas M . The fading channel model has been used.

the receive filters and the training pilot sequences length. The most noticeable fact by observing Figure 4.16 is that the MRC filter don't reach the maximum capacity of 2 bits per channel use, not even at high SNR. It maintains the mutual information almost constant at 1.9 bits per channel use at high SNR, while using the fading channel reached 2 bits per channel use at 0 dB for all the pilot training sequence length. However, the ZF receive filter don't reach either the maximum of 2 bits per channel user, although it is very close to reach it. And now the ZF, just as the MRC, needs a slightly better SNR than using the fading model to reach the same Mutual Information. In general the results are equivalent with the presented in Figure 4.3, where the MRC receive filter had a poor performance compared with the ZF, and in general, both receive filters had a worse performance.

Figure 4.16: Mutual Information versus SNR for $M=400$ and $K=20$. The ZF and MRC filters are considered for both the cases of perfect and imperfect CSI. The training sequence length depends on the number of users K . The mmWave channel model has been used.

Finally, to finish this section, we have depicted the mutual information versus the SNR in Figures 4.17 and 4.18 for two more system parameters, which we will use to compare with the beamforming in the following section. This two cases uses 10 single-antenna users and 200 BS antennas, and 5 single-antenna users and 100 BS antennas. And both uses 2 clusters and 10 rays per cluster. Comparing Figure 4.16 with Figures 4.17 and 4.18, we observe that using 20 single-antenna users and 400 BS antennas we obtain better performance at low SNR for both, the ZF and the MRC. We observe so, that the performance is directly related with the number of BS antennas for the ZF receive filter, and for the MRC is also related to the number of single-antenna users. If we focus at low SNR, using 10 users and 200 BS antennas, and 5 users and 100 BS antennas it shows similar results, obtaining a Mutual information between 0.2 bits per channel use and 0.8 bits per channel use depending on the pilot training sequence length considered. Although the performance for the ZF of using 5 users and 100 BS antennas

is slightly lower, and for the MRC is slightly higher, which reaffirms what we have already said, that the performance of the mutual information for the ZF is directly related with the number of antennas at the BS, and for the MRC is more related with the number of users. If we focus at high SNR we observe as the three considered cases has similar results, obtaining values close to the maximum channel capacity of 2. But again there are slightly differences between the three cases and the receive filter considered. The case with more antennas reach the maximum available capacity before than the other two, although that for the MRC it is slight lower than the other two cases. Notice also that while the performance for the ZF receive filter for the system with more BS antennas is higher, for the MRC filter is the other way round. We obtain better performance for the MRC using less antennas and hence less users. This is due to the features of each filter, which as we already said, the ZF cancel the interference between users by forcing it to 0, while the MRC does not. So the MRC filter is more affected to the inter-user interferences, and hence the mutual information performance is increased as less users are.

Figure 4.17: Mutual Information versus SNR for $M=200$ and $K=10$. The ZF and MRC filters are considered for both the cases of perfect and imperfect CSI. The training sequence length depends on the number of users K . The mmWave channel model has been used.

Figure 4.18: Mutual Information versus SNR for $M=100$ and $K=5$. The ZF and MRC filters are considered for both the cases of perfect and imperfect CSI. The training sequence length depends on the number of users K . The mmWave channel model has been used.

4.2.2 Mutual Information with analog beamforming applied

In this section are depicted the results of Mutual Information with beamforming applied and diverse parameters configurations. Then the results are compared for beamforming applied and without it, in order to evaluate the performance of the system and measure if there is a Mutual information improvement by using it. Basically, we have simulated the same cases described in section 4.1.2 for the SER, but now for the Mutual Information.

In Figure 4.19 is depicted the Mutual Information using 10 single-antenna users and 200 antennas in the BS, 2 clusters per user and 10 rays per cluster, 5 beams per cluster and a cluster beam separation of 0.4° deg. Comparing the results obtained using beamforming with the results without applying it shown in Figure 4.17, we observe that, as it happened in the performance of the SER, the Mutual Information performance is inferior using beamforming for both receive filters. The most noticeable fact is that using beamforming, the mutual information at low SNR is extremely low, about 0.1-0.2 bits per channel use for all the considered receive filters and pilot sequence training length. Without beamforming it takes a value between 0.2 bits per channel use for the case with pilot training length of $N = 5K$ and 0.8 bits per channel use for the case with pilot training length of $N = 50K$ and full CSI, which is slightly higher. From -5 dB, in the case without beamforming the ZF filter takes a value close to 2 bits per channel use for all the considered cases and both receive filters, while using beamforming it takes a value about 1.6 bits per channel use for the ZF receive filter and about 1.1 bits per channel use for the MRC. From 0 dB in the case with no beamforming applied the Mutual Information remains almost constant to 2 bits per channel use for the ZF case and slightly inferior for the MRC, but

both really close to the maximum of 2 bits per channel use. However using beamforming the maximum Mutual Information reached is 1.8 bits per channel use for the ZF and about 1.4 bits per channel use for the MRC, which means that, as we expected after see the results for SER, in this particular case with this ratio of users/antennas and the selected beamforming parameters, the beamforming don't provide any improvement related to the performance. The advantage of using beamforming in that situation is the reduction of the system dimensionality and number of quantizers, since we are using 5 beams per cluster (which are 100 beams in total, inferior to the number of BS antennas that is 200), and hence reducing the power consumption of the system.

Figure 4.19: Mutual Information versus SNR for $M=200$ and $K=10$. It is considered 2 cluster per user, 10 rays per cluster, 6 beam per cluster, beam separation 0.4° deg and Laplacian PDF standard deviation 0.25. The ZF and MRC filters are considered for both the cases of perfect and imperfect CSI.

In Figure 4.20 is depicted the Mutual Information for 5 single-antenna users and 100 antennas in the BS, 2 clusters per user and 10 rays per cluster, 5 beams per cluster and a cluster beam separation of 0.1° deg. In Figure 4.21 we have used the same parameters than in Figure 4.20, but doubling the beams per cluster from 5 to 10, in order to show the effect in the Mutual Information provoked by doubling it. Then the three cases are compared in Figure 4.22 for the channel estimation with a pilot training length of $N = 50K$. In Figure 4.22 can be observed that by not using beamforming, we have better Mutual Information performance than using it, for both the MRC and ZF filters. Although the performance of the beamforming for the ZF with 10 beams is very close to the case without beamforming. For both cases with beamforming the performance of the MRC receive filter is far from the performance without beamforming, above all at high SNR. We also observe that both beamforming cases offer similar performance, although the beamforming with 10 beams offers slightly better performance, as expected. In Figure 4.9 we have seen as the case with beamforming and 10 beams per cluster had better SER

performance even compared without beamforming, but in case where we evaluate the Mutual Information that is not achieved.

Figure 4.20: Mutual Information versus SNR or $M=100$ and $K=5$. It is considered 2 cluster per user, 10 rays per cluster, 5 beam per cluster, beam separation 0.1° deg and Laplacian PDF standard deviation 0.25. The ZF and MRC filters are considered for both the cases of perfect and imperfect CSI.

In Figure 4.23 is depicted a detailed comparison between without use beamforming and using beamforming with 10 beams per cluster. As can be observed for both receive filters the performance of the system without beamforming is in general better. Without beamforming the maximum Mutual Information reached is about 1.9 bits per channel use for the MRC and practically 2 bits per channel use for the ZF, however, using beamforming and 10 beams per cluster, the maximum Mutual Information reached is 1.6 bits per channel use for the MRC and about 1.9 bits per channel use for the ZF. At low SNR the performance for both the beamforming and without it is quite similar, above all for the channel estimation with pilot training length $N = 10K$ and $N = 5K$ for ZF an MRC filters. So by using beamforming and 10 beams, it do not offer any performance improvement, and there is not also any reduction in the dimensionality of the system or the number of quantizers used, since we are using 10 beams per cluster, which are 100 beams in total, equal to the number of BS antennas.

In Figure 4.24 is depicted a comparison between the system without and with beamforming applied, with 5 single-antenna users and 100 BS antennas, 2 clusters per user and 10 rays per cluster, and a beam separation of 0.1° deg. Using this parameters the total number of beams is 80, since $d = 5 \text{ users} \cdot 8 \text{ beams per cluster} \cdot 2 \text{ cluster per cluster} = 80$. Which is noticeably lower than the number of antennas in the BS, unlike the previous case where we had 100 beams. As can be observed the results are very similar to the presented in Figure 4.23, but now we are using less beams, and therefore the dimensionality of the system and the number of quantizers are reduced. Focusing the attention on the MRC receive filter, we observe that the Mutual

Figure 4.21: Mutual Information versus SNR or $M=100$ and $K=5$. It is considered 2 cluster per user, 10 rays per cluster, 10 beam per cluster, beam separation 0.1° deg and Laplacian PDF standard deviation 0.25. The ZF and MRC filters are considered for both the cases of perfect and imperfect CSI.

Figure 4.22: Mutual Information versus SNR for $M=100$ and $K=5$. It is considered 3 different cases, 2 with beamforming and another without it. We also consider 2 cluster per user, 10 rays per cluster, 5 or 10 beam per cluster, beam separation 1° deg and Laplacian PDF standard deviation 0.25. The ZF and MRC filters are considered for both imperfect CSI with $N = 50K$ pilot training length.

Figure 4.23: Mutual Information per user versus SNR for $M=100$ and $K=5$. It is considered the case with beamforming and 10 beams and without beamforming. The MRC (top) and ZF (bottom) filters are considered for both the cases of perfect and imperfect CSI.

information performance is poorer with beamforming. Focusing the attention in the ZF, we observe that it is also slightly lower, as we expected from the results showed above in the last comparison. In the previous subsection we have showed the same comparison, but for the SER, and we have seen as approximately both systems had the same performance. But unfortunately, evaluating the Mutual Information this not happens.

Figure 4.24: Mutual Information per user versus SNR for $M=100$ and $K=5$. It is considered the case with beamforming and 8 beams and without beamforming. The MRC (top) and ZF (bottom) filters are considered for both the cases of perfect and imperfect CSI.

In Figure 4.25 is depicted a comparison between using and not using the phase correction matrix D and the effects of it in the performance of the Mutual Information. We have used the same system parameters than in the last example. As can be observed, by both the MRC and ZF receive filter, the performance using the phase correction matrix is much better, as expected. Using the matrix D we are correcting properly the phase shift induced by the effective channel,

and hence we obtain a better performance. The same happened in the previous subsection with the SER.

Figure 4.25: Mutual Information per user versus SNR for $M=100$ and $K=5$. It is considered the case with beamforming and 8 beams with and without apply the phase correction matrix D . The MRC (top) and ZF (bottom) filters are considered for both the cases of perfect and imperfect CSI.

Finally, in Figure 4.26 is depicted a comparison between two different Laplace sigma standard deviations, which controls the scatter of the rays. We have chosen $\sigma = 0.1$ and $\sigma = 1$. Figure 4.26 shows results similar to the presented on the SER section. In the case where the standard deviation is bigger the Mutual Information is lower, due to that the rays are more scattered, this produces that the clusters get bigger, which produces a deterioration of the performance due to that the beams are not able to receive most of the rays of the clusters.

Figure 4.26: Mutual Information per user versus SNR for $M=100$ and $K=5$. It is considered the case with beamforming and 8 beams using two different Laplace PDF standard deviation, $\sigma = 0.1$ and $\sigma = 1$. The MRC (top) and ZF (bottom) filters are considered for both the cases of perfect and imperfect CSI.

5 Conclusions

In this, the last section of the document, we present the conclusions about the performance of a massive MIMO uplink system that employs 1-bit ADCs and mmWaves. In first place we have presented the system model without beamforming and with the fading channel model, whose system model we have used later to apply the analog beamforming on it. Then we have presented a different channel model, called the clustered channel model, which fits the performance of the mmWave. After show the main features of the mmWave channel model and some examples, we have presented the system model with analog beamforming, which we have used to show the main results of this project. After show some examples with the beamforming system model, we have proceed to show the performance metrics of the system that we chose to evaluate, which are two: The Symbol Error Rate and the Mutual Information. We have described two methods to compute it, by means of Monte Carlo simulations, which consists in do many realizations of the transmit vector x and vector noise n , and by means of an analytical approach for the MRC filters. We showed that the results based on the analytical analysis fit well to the Monte Carlo results. Thanks to the closed-form derivation of the symbol estimate PMF, the computational complexity is noticeably reduced in the sense that a symbol and channel noise vectors Monte Carlo simulation is avoided.

The obtained results without beamforming applied shows that when the SNR is larger than a certain value, all the filters achieve the maximal possible QPSK capacity, whatever the training sequence length is. Besides the performance of the SER when the SNR is larger than a certain value, we consider it is enough to satisfy the demands of the users. Hence we have showed that massive MIMO systems exhibit good performance even when employing 1-bit receive signal quantization. After change the channel model to the mmWave model, the obtained results have been approximately the same for both the SER and the Mutual Information, although the performance of the entire system has been slightly deteriorated due to the effects provoked by the mmWaves.

Then in order to reduce the system dimensionality and number of quantizers, and obtain a higher performance by potentially lower energy consumption we applied analog beamforming to the system. In first place we have simulated the communication system for 10 single antenna

users and 200 BS antennas. With this parameters we did not observe any noticeable improvement by using beamforming in any performance metrics, the SER or Mutual Information. This could be due to the number of users, which could be too much for the chosen beamforming parameters.

After reducing the number of users and BS antennas from 10 to 5 users and from 200 to 100 BS antennas, we analysed again the performance of the system. The results showed that using 5 beams per cluster, the SER performance was not as good as the non beamforming. The same happened for the Mutual Information. So the performance of using 5 beams was not considered enough to satisfy the requirements of the system. Then we compared the same system, but doubling the number of beams to 10. By that way and focusing the attention on the SER we observed an improvement of about 2 dB for both, the MRC and ZF for pilot training sequence length $N = 50K$ and Full CSI. For the rest of the sequences lengths the improvement was even higher. Focusing the attention on the Mutual Information we observed that the performance for the MRC filter using beamforming and 10 beams was not as good as without beamforming. Although for the ZF receive filter we observed that from -5 dB of SNR, both performances were quite similar, but still slightly worse compared to the system without beamforming. For example at 0 dB, the differences between the beamforming and without beamforming for the ZF receive filter is less than 0.2 bits per channel, positive results for without beamforming. So by using 10 beams, 5 users and 100 BS antennas the beamforming showed an incredible SER performance and a more than enough Mutual information performance for the ZF receive filter. For the MRC receive filter both performance metrics are too much low to consider that there is an improvement by using beamforming. The only disadvantage using beamforming is that by using 10 beams per cluster, we are using 100 beams in total, which is the number of antennas. So by that way is not reduced the system dimensionality or the number of quantizers of the system. But we obtain a higher system performance and potentially lower energy consumption, since for obtain the same system SNR, the users can transmit with less power, which is traduced in better battery life of the user devices.

Then we have reduced the number of beams from 10 to 8 in order to be able to reduce the system dimensionality of the system, although loosing some performance compared with the previous case. The results showed that the SER performance was very similar for both, the beamforming and without it. The mutual information showed practically the same in both cases, although loosing some performance, above all at high SNR for both, the MRC and the ZF. This performance loss was about 0.3 bits per channel use for the MRC and about 0.1 bits per channel use for the ZF. Which can be assumed perfectly. Even more knowing that using 8 beams, the system dimensionality and number of quantizers is reduced in 20. So by loosing a bit of Mutual Information performance, the system with beamforming will be more power efficient and obtaining the same SER performance.

Then we have analysed the effects induced into the system by not using the phase correction

matrix in the receiver. The obtained results showed as if we do not use it, the performance of the entire system gets noticeable worse for the SER. The Mutual information performance was quite similar using or not the phase correction matrix, although slightly worse without use it.

Finally we have compared two different values of Laplacian PDF standard deviation, which controls the scatter of the users rays, and hence the cluster dimensions. The results showed as the bigger the variance is, the scatter of the rays are bigger, and hence the obtained performance of the system is lower.

In conclusion, we could say that beamforming MIMO systems employing 1-bit ADCs and mmWaves can achieve better performance at reduced dimensionality than a system without beamforming. As we have seen, equalising the number of antennas to the number of beams (for example to 100) we don not reduce the number of quantizers or the dimensionality of the system, but we can accomplish much better performance that not using beamforming. We have also seen that reducing a certain number of the total beams respect the number of BS antennas (for example 80 beams and 100 BS antennas) we can accomplish similar system performance than not using beamforming, but by that way, we can also reduce considerably the dimensionality of the system and the number of quantizers. In addition, the obtained results show that beamforming is more applicable to systems with less BS antennas, and hence users.

A Matlab code

Symbol Transmission:

```
function [y,x,r] = SymbolTransmission(Parameters, H_Full_CSI, n_power)

%Function which simulates the symbols transmissions of the K users through
%the channel, then is received by the M antennas and quantized with a 1-bit ADC
x = ones(Parameters.K,1);%initialize the vector x which contain the symbols sent by the users
for i = 1:Parameters.K
    j = randi(4);%selector of symbol to transmit 1 = 1/sqrt(2)*(1+j), 2 = 1/sqrt(2)*(1-j),
    x(i)= Parameters.QPSK(j); %3 = 1/sqrt(2)*(-1-j) and 4 = 1/sqrt(2)*(-1+j)
end
n = sqrt(n_power / 2) * (randn(Parameters.M,1)+1j*randn(Parameters.M,1));%Complex gaussian noise.
r = sqrt(Parameters.P_tx)*H_Full_CSI*x+n;%Discrete-time complex baseband received signal at the ...
    base station (Eq.1)
y = sign(real(r))+1j*sign(imag(r));%received quantized signal with 1 bit ADC
```

Symbol Estimation:

```
function [x_est_decisor_ZF, x_est_decisor_MRC] = SymbolEstimation (y, A_ZF_Full_CSI, ...
    A_MRC_Full_CSI, A_ZF_HestN50,...
    A_ZF_HestN10, A_ZF_HestN5,A_MRC_HestN50, ...
    A_MRC_HestN10, A_MRC_HestN5);%Function which ...
    estimate the received symbols and applies the ...
    decisor

%Soft Estimation of X. y is the quantized received signal an A is the receive filter
x_est_ZF_Full_CSI = A_ZF_Full_CSI * y;%Soft estimate of the transmitted symbols with A_ZF (Eq.3)
x_est_MRC_Full_CSI = A_MRC_Full_CSI' * y;%Soft estimate of the transmitted symbols with A_MRC ...
    (Eq.3), we need to do the Hermitian
x_est_ZF_HestN50 = A_ZF_HestN50 * y;
x_est_ZF_HestN10 = A_ZF_HestN10 * y;
x_est_ZF_HestN5 = A_ZF_HestN5 * y;
x_est_MRC_HestN50 = A_MRC_HestN50' * y;
x_est_MRC_HestN10 = A_MRC_HestN10' * y;
x_est_MRC_HestN5 = A_MRC_HestN5' * y;
%% ...

-----
%Decisor: After using the filter A, the amplitude of the estimated symbol needs to be corrected,
%in order to be able to compare the received and sent symbols.
x_est_ZF_decis_Full_CSI = ...
    ((1/sqrt(2))*(sign(real(x_est_ZF_Full_CSI))+1j*sign(imag(x_est_ZF_Full_CSI))));
x_est_MRC_decis_Full_CSI = ...
    ((1/sqrt(2))*(sign(real(x_est_MRC_Full_CSI))+1j*sign(imag(x_est_MRC_Full_CSI))));
x_est_ZF_decis_HestN50 = (1/sqrt(2)) * (sign(real(x_est_ZF_HestN50))+1j*sign(imag(x_est_ZF_HestN50)));
x_est_ZF_decis_HestN10 = (1/sqrt(2))*(sign(real(x_est_ZF_HestN10))+1j*sign(imag(x_est_ZF_HestN10)));
```

```

x_est_ZF_decis_HestN5 = (1/sqrt(2))*(sign(real(x_est_ZF_HestN5))+1j*sign(imag(x_est_ZF_HestN5)));
x_est_MRC_decis_HestN50 = (1/sqrt(2))*(sign(real(x_est_MRC_HestN50))+1j*sign(imag(x_est_MRC_HestN50)));
x_est_MRC_decis_HestN10 = (1/sqrt(2))*(sign(real(x_est_MRC_HestN10))+1j*sign(imag(x_est_MRC_HestN10)));
x_est_MRC_decis_HestN5 = (1/sqrt(2))*(sign(real(x_est_MRC_HestN5))+1j*sign(imag(x_est_MRC_HestN5)));
%% ...
-----
%all the symbols are put into the same matrix. Each column is a channel case
x_est_decisor_ZF =[x_est_ZF_decis_Full_CSI'; x_est_ZF_decis_HestN50'; x_est_ZF_decis_HestN10'; ...
    x_est_ZF_decis_HestN5'];
x_est_decisor_MRC =[x_est_MRC_decis_Full_CSI'; x_est_MRC_decis_HestN50'; x_est_MRC_decis_HestN10'; ...
    x_est_MRC_decis_HestN5'];

```

Channel Estimation:

```

function [Hest_N50,Hest_N10,Hest_N5] = Channel_H_Estimation(H_Full_CSI, n_power, Parameters)

if Parameters.ChannelOption == 1
    N_50 = 50*Parameters.K;%Number of training sequences
    N_10 = 10*Parameters.K;
    N_5 = 5*Parameters.K;
else
    N_50 = 50*Parameters.M;
    N_10 = 10*Parameters.M;
    N_5 = 5*Parameters.M;
end
%%
%Case N=50
X_N50 = zeros(Parameters.K,N_50);
for seq = 1:N_50
    x = ones(Parameters.K,1);
    for i = 1:Parameters.K
        j = randi(4);%selector of symbol to transmit
        x(i)= Parameters.QPSK(j);
    end
    X_N50(:,seq) = x;
end
n = sqrt(n_power / 2) * (randn(Parameters.M,N_50)+1j*randn(Parameters.M,N_50));
r_N50 = sqrt(Parameters.P_tx)*H_Full_CSI*X_N50+n;
Y_N50 = sign(real(r_N50))+1j*sign(imag(r_N50));
Hest_N50 = (1/sqrt(Parameters.P_tx))*(Y_N50*X_N50')*inv(X_N50*X_N50');
%%
%Case N=10
X_N10 = zeros(Parameters.K,N_10);
for seq = 1:N_10
    x = ones(Parameters.K,1);
    for i = 1:Parameters.K
        j = randi(4);%selector of symbol to transmit
        x(i)= Parameters.QPSK(j);
    end
    X_N10(:,seq) = x;
end
n = sqrt(n_power / 2) * (randn(Parameters.M,N_10)+1j*randn(Parameters.M,N_10));
r_N10 = sqrt(Parameters.P_tx)*H_Full_CSI*X_N10+n;
Y_N10 = sign(real(r_N10))+1j*sign(imag(r_N10));
Hest_N10 = 1/sqrt(Parameters.P_tx)*(Y_N10*X_N10')*inv(X_N10*X_N10');
%%
%Case N=5
X_N5 = zeros(Parameters.K,N_5);
for seq = 1:N_5
    x = ones(Parameters.K,1);
    for i = 1:Parameters.K
        j = randi(4);%selector of symbol to transmit

```

```

        x(i) = Parameters.QPSK(j);
    end
    X_N5(:, seq) = x;
end
n = sqrt(n.power / 2) * (randn(Parameters.M, N_5) + 1j * randn(Parameters.M, N_5));
r_N5 = sqrt(Parameters.P.tx) * H_Full_CSI * X_N5 + n;
Y_N5 = sign(real(r_N5)) + 1j * sign(imag(r_N5));
Hest_N5 = 1/sqrt(Parameters.P.tx) * (Y_N5 * X_N5') * inv(X_N5 * X_N5');
end

```

Receive Filters Estimation:

```

function [A_ZF_Full_CSI, A_MRC_Full_CSI, A_ZF_HestN50, A_ZF_HestN10, A_ZF_HestN5, ...
        A_MRC_HestN50, A_MRC_HestN10, A_MRC_HestN5] = ...
    Estimation.Filters(H_tot, Parameters) %Function wich compute the ZF and MRC ...
    receive filters
%Estimation of the Receive filter AZ
A_ZF_Full_CSI = pinv(H_tot(:, :, 1)); %Receive Filter A^Herm using Zero Forcing (Eq 9)
A_ZF_HestN50 = pinv(H_tot(:, :, 2));
A_ZF_HestN10 = pinv(H_tot(:, :, 3));
A_ZF_HestN5 = pinv(H_tot(:, :, 4));
%% ...
-----
%Estimation of the Receive filter MRC
for c = 1:Parameters.K %Receive Filter A MRC (Maximum-Ratio-Combining) using equation (8)
    A_MRC_Full_CSI(:, c) = (H_tot(:, c, 1)) / ((norm(H_tot(:, c, 1)))^2);
    A_MRC_HestN50(:, c) = (H_tot(:, c, 2)) / ((norm(H_tot(:, c, 2)))^2);
    A_MRC_HestN10(:, c) = (H_tot(:, c, 3)) / ((norm(H_tot(:, c, 3)))^2);
    A_MRC_HestN5(:, c) = (H_tot(:, c, 4)) / ((norm(H_tot(:, c, 4)))^2);
end

```

MmWave Channel model:

```

function [H_mmWave, Cluster_Center_deg_tot] = mmWave_Channel(Parameters)
%This function makes use of the laplace pdf to simulate the rays of each
%user. There are also computed the cluster centres and the channel model,
%at it is explained in section 2.2 of the thesis
Cluster_Center_deg_tot = [];
for k = 1:Parameters.K
    %it is used the function laplacepdf to compute the rays of each
    %user per cluster, following the laplacian PDF
    Phi_Rx_deg = ...
        laplacepdf(Parameters.N_ray_Cluster, Parameters.N_Cluster, Parameters.LaplaceVariance);
    Cluster_Center_deg = -60 + (60+60)*rand(1, Parameters.N_Cluster); %Angular position in degrees ...
        of each cluster center [-60,60]
    Cluster_Center_deg_tot = [Cluster_Center_deg_tot, Cluster_Center_deg]; %vector which contains ...
        every cluster center
    col = 1; %its used to reset the variable col in order to reuse it
    clear A_Rx; %we clear the variable RX in order to reuse it
    for l = 1:Parameters.N_Cluster %it is computed the steering vector A for each antenna M
        for i = 1:Parameters.N_ray_Cluster
            for m = 1:Parameters.M
                Arx(m) = 1/sqrt(Parameters.M) * ...
                    exp(1j * (m-1) * pi * sin(Cluster_Center_deg(l) + Phi_Rx_deg(i, 1))); %steering vector
            end
            A_Rx(:, col) = Arx;
            col = col + 1;
        end
    end
    Alpha_il = (1/sqrt(2)) * (randn(Parameters.N_ray_Cluster, Parameters.N_Cluster) ...

```

```

        +1j*randn(Parameters.N_ray_Cluster,Parameters.N_Cluster));%Rayleigh channel coefficient
%%
    col=1;
    for l=1:Parameters.N_Cluster
        for i=1:Parameters.N_ray_Cluster
            A(:,col)=(Alpha_il(i,l)*A.Rx(:,col));
            col=col+1;
        end
    end
    %it is computed h for each user
    H_mmWave(:,k) = sqrt(Parameters.M/(Parameters.N_Cluster*Parameters.N_ray_Cluster))*sum(A,2);
end
end
end

```

Laplace PDF generation:

```

function laplrnd = laplacepdf(number1,number2,Sigma.Phi)
B = 1/(1-exp(-sqrt(2)*pi/Sigma.Phi));
Phi = -pi:0.001:pi;
P = nan(length(Phi),1);
for iter=1:length(Phi)
    if Phi(iter) < pi && Phi(iter) ≥ 0
        P(iter) = ((B*exp(-abs(sqrt(2)*Phi(iter)/Sigma.Phi)))/(sqrt(2)*Sigma.Phi));
    elseif Phi(iter) ≥ -pi && Phi(iter) ≤ 0
        P(iter) = ((B*exp(-abs(sqrt(2)*Phi(iter)/Sigma.Phi)))/(sqrt(2)*Sigma.Phi));
    else
        P(iter)=0;
    end
end
% create cdf
cdf = cumtrapz(Phi, P);
% keep only the unique values: needed for interpolation
idx_mid = (Phi < pi) & (Phi ≥ -pi);
cdf = cdf(idx_mid);
Phi = Phi(idx_mid);
P = P(idx_mid);
% number of required random draws
n1 = number1;
n2 = number2;
% generate uniformly distributed random numbers from [0,1]
r = rand(number1,number2);
% generate random numbers from the desired pdf; inverse transform sampling
laplrnd = interp1(cdf, Phi, r);
% Verification plot
% [f,x] = hist(laplrnd,100);
%
% bar(x,f/trapz(x,f))
% hold on
% plot(Phi, P, 'red', 'Linewidth', 1.2)
% legend('histogram from random values', 'analytical pdf')
end

```

SER for Random Channel:

```

%Random Channel Matrix Generation
H_Full_CSI = ...
    (1/sqrt(2))*(randn(Parameters.M,Parameters.K)+1j*randn(Parameters.M,Parameters.K));%Channel ...
    Matrix known by the BS, Rayleigh distribution

for Pot = 1:length(Parameters.NoisePowerSER)%Choose the power from vector NoisePowerSER

```

```

%%
n_power = Parameters.NoisePowerSER(Pot);%Selected noise to simulate with
[Hest_N50,Hest_N10,Hest_N5] = Channel_H_Estimation(H.Full_CSI, n_power,Parameters);%function ...
    that estimate the channel using 3 different training lengths
H_tot = cat(3, H.Full_CSI, Hest_N50, Hest_N10, Hest_N5);%Multidimensional matrix with all the ...
    channel matrix
%% ...
-----
[A_ZF_Full_CSI, A_MRC_Full_CSI, A_ZF_HestN50, A_ZF_HestN10, A_ZF_HestN5,...
 A_MRC_HestN50, A_MRC_HestN10, A_MRC_HestN5] = ...
    Estimation_Filters(H_tot, Parameters); %Function wich compute the ZF and MRC receive ...
    filters
%% ...
-----
for Sim = 1:Parameters.Simulations;%Number of Monte Carlo Simulations of 'n' and 'x'
%%
[y,x] = Symbol_Transmission(Parameters, H.Full_CSI, n_power);%function which simulates the ...
    symbols tranimssion and reception+quantization
%% ...
-----
if Parameters.MonteCarloChoice == 1
%% ...
-----
[x_est_decisor_ZF, x_est_decisor_MRC] = Symbol_Estimation (y, A_ZF_Full_CSI, ...
    A_MRC_Full_CSI, A_ZF_HestN50,...
    A_ZF_HestN10, ...
    A_ZF_HestN5,A_MRC_HestN50, ...
    A_MRC_HestN10, ...
    A_MRC_HestN5);%Function which ...
    estimate the received symbols ...
    and applies the decisor
%% ...
-----
%It is computed the symbol estimated error using symerr, whose function
%give us the ratio directly
[~, Ratio.MRC_Full_CSI (Sim,Pot)] = symerr(x,x_est_decisor_MRC(:,1));
[~, Ratio.MRC_HestN50 (Sim,Pot)] = symerr(x,x_est_decisor_MRC(:,2));
[~, Ratio.MRC_HestN10 (Sim,Pot)] = symerr(x,x_est_decisor_MRC(:,3));
[~, Ratio.MRC_HestN5 (Sim,Pot)] = symerr(x,x_est_decisor_MRC(:,4));
[~, Ratio.ZF_Full_CSI (Sim,Pot)] = symerr(x,x_est_decisor_ZF(:,1));
[~, Ratio.ZF_HestN50 (Sim,Pot)] = symerr(x,x_est_decisor_ZF(:,2));
[~, Ratio.ZF_HestN10 (Sim,Pot)] = symerr(x,x_est_decisor_ZF(:,3));
[~, Ratio.ZF_HestN5 (Sim,Pot)] = symerr(x,x_est_decisor_ZF(:,4));
assignin('base','Ratio',Ratio)
end
%% ...
-----
if Parameters.AnalyticalChoice == 1
    Analytical_Approach_SER; %to compute the annalytical approach
    assignin('base','ResultAnalytical',ResultAnalytical)
end
end
end
%% ...
-----
%Plot of Fig.5 Paper + Analytical/Monte Carlo comparison
Plot_SER;

```

SER for MmWave Channel with Beamforming:

```
[H_mmWave.Full_CSI, Cluster.Center_deg_tot] = mmWave_Channel(Parameters);%Mmwave Channel Model ...
```

```

generation
%%
for Pot=1:length(Parameters.NoisePowerSER)%it Choose the power from vector NoisePowerSER

n_power = Parameters.NoisePowerSER(Pot);%Selected noise to simulate with
[Hest_N50,Hest_N10,Hest_N5] = Channel_H_Estimation(H_mmWave_Full_CSI, ...
    n_power,Parameters);%function which estimate the channel using 3 different training lenghts
H_tot = cat(3, H_mmWave_Full_CSI, Hest_N50, Hest_N10, Hest_N5);%Multidimensional matrix with all ...
    the channel matrix
%% ...
-----
[B, H_Effective, D] = Beamforming(Parameters,H_tot,Cluster_Center_deg_tot);%Function that ...
    compute the beamers and the parameters of the beamforming
%% ...
-----
[A_ZF_Full_CSI, A_MRC_Full_CSI, A_ZF_HestN50, A_ZF_HestN10, A_ZF_HestN5,...
    A_MRC_HestN50, A_MRC_HestN10, A_MRC_HestN5] = ...
    Estimation_Filters_Beamforming(H_Effective, D, Parameters); %Function wich compute the ZF ...
    and MRC receive filters
%%
for Sim=1:Parameters.Simulations%Number of Monte Carlo Simulations of 'n' and 'x'
%%
[y,x,r] = Symbol_Transmission(Parameters, H_mmWave_Full_CSI, n_power);%function which ...
    simulates the symbols tranimssion and reception+quiantization
%% ...
-----
if Parameters.MonteCarloChoice == 1
    for Sel=1:4%selector of the four beamforming matrix

        r_Q = B(:, :,Sel)*r;
        yq(:,Sel) = sign(real(r_Q))+1j*sign(imag(r_Q));
    end
%% ...
-----
[x_est_decisor_ZF, x_est_decisor_MRC] = Symbol_Estimation_Beamforming(yq, ...
    A_ZF_Full_CSI, A_MRC_Full_CSI, A_ZF_HestN50,...
    A_ZF_HestN10, A_ZF_HestN5,A_MRC_HestN50, ...
    A_MRC_HestN10, A_MRC_HestN5);%Function which ...
    estimate the received symbols and applies the ...
    decisor
%% ...
-----
%It is computed the symbol estimated error using symerr, whose function
%give us the ratio directly
[~, Ratio_MRC_Full_CSI(Sim,Pot)] = symerr(x,x_est_decisor_MRC(:,1));
[~, Ratio_MRC_HestN50(Sim,Pot)] = symerr(x,x_est_decisor_MRC(:,2));
[~, Ratio_MRC_HestN10(Sim,Pot)] = symerr(x,x_est_decisor_MRC(:,3));
[~, Ratio_MRC_HestN5(Sim,Pot)] = symerr(x,x_est_decisor_MRC(:,4));
[~, Ratio_ZF_Full_CSI(Sim,Pot)] = symerr(x,x_est_decisor_ZF(:,1));
[~, Ratio_ZF_HestN50(Sim,Pot)] = symerr(x,x_est_decisor_ZF(:,2));
[~, Ratio_ZF_HestN10(Sim,Pot)] = symerr(x,x_est_decisor_ZF(:,3));
[~, Ratio_ZF_HestN5(Sim,Pot)] = symerr(x,x_est_decisor_ZF(:,4));
assignin('base','Ratio',Ratio)
end
%% ...
-----
if Parameters.AnalyticalChoice == 1

    Analytical_Approach_Beamforming_SER; %to compute the annalytical approach
end
end
end
%% ...
-----
%Plot of Fig.5 Paper + Analytical/Monte Carlo comparison

```

```
Plot_SER;
```

SER computation function:

```
%It is computed the symbol estimated error using symerr, which function
%give us the ratio directly
[~, Ratio.MRC.Full_CSI(Sim,Pot)] = symerr(x,x.est.decisor_MRC(:,1));
[~, Ratio.MRC.HestN50(Sim,Pot)] = symerr(x,x.est.decisor_MRC(:,2));
[~, Ratio.MRC.HestN10(Sim,Pot)] = symerr(x,x.est.decisor_MRC(:,3));
[~, Ratio.MRC.HestN5(Sim,Pot)] = symerr(x,x.est.decisor_MRC(:,4));
[~, Ratio.ZF.Full_CSI(Sim,Pot)] = symerr(x,x.est.decisor_ZF(:,1));
[~, Ratio.ZF.HestN50(Sim,Pot)] = symerr(x,x.est.decisor_ZF(:,2));
[~, Ratio.ZF.HestN10(Sim,Pot)] = symerr(x,x.est.decisor_ZF(:,3));
[~, Ratio.ZF.HestN5(Sim,Pot)] = symerr(x,x.est.decisor_ZF(:,4));
assignin('base','Ratio',Ratio)
```

Plot SER function:

```
if Parameters.MonteCarloChoice == 1
    ResultMonteCarlo.SER_ZF_Full_CSI_Num = sum(Ratio.ZF.Full_CSI)/Sim;
    ResultMonteCarlo.SER_MRC_Full_CSI_Num = sum(Ratio.MRC.Full_CSI)/Sim;
    ResultMonteCarlo.SER_ZF_Hest50_Num = sum(Ratio.ZF.HestN50)/Sim;
    ResultMonteCarlo.SER_ZF_Hest10_Num = sum(Ratio.ZF.HestN10)/Sim;
    ResultMonteCarlo.SER_ZF_Hest5_Num = sum(Ratio.ZF.HestN5)/Sim;
    ResultMonteCarlo.SER_MRC_Hest50_Num = sum(Ratio.MRC.HestN50)/Sim;
    ResultMonteCarlo.SER_MRC_Hest10_Num = sum(Ratio.MRC.HestN10)/Sim;
    ResultMonteCarlo.SER_MRC_Hest5_Num = sum(Ratio.MRC.HestN5)/Sim;
    assignin('base','ResultMonteCarlo',ResultMonteCarlo)
    if Parameters.ChannelOption == 1

        figure(1)%Plot of Fig.5 Paper
        semilogy(Parameters.SNR_SER_dB,ResultMonteCarlo.SER_ZF_Full_CSI_Num,'-rs');
        hold on
        semilogy(Parameters.SNR_SER_dB,ResultMonteCarlo.SER_MRC_Full_CSI_Num,'-bs');
        hold on
        semilogy(Parameters.SNR_SER_dB,ResultMonteCarlo.SER_ZF_Hest50_Num,'--rs');
        hold on
        semilogy(Parameters.SNR_SER_dB,ResultMonteCarlo.SER_ZF_Hest10_Num,':rs');
        hold on
        semilogy(Parameters.SNR_SER_dB,ResultMonteCarlo.SER_ZF_Hest5_Num,'-.rs');
        hold on
        semilogy(Parameters.SNR_SER_dB,ResultMonteCarlo.SER_MRC_Hest50_Num,'--bs');
        hold on
        semilogy(Parameters.SNR_SER_dB,ResultMonteCarlo.SER_MRC_Hest10_Num,':bs');
        hold on
        semilogy(Parameters.SNR_SER_dB,ResultMonteCarlo.SER_MRC_Hest5_Num,'-.bs');
        legend('ZF, full CSI','MRC, Full CSI', 'ZF, Channel Estimation, N=50K',...
            'ZF, Channel Estimation, N=10K', 'ZF, Channel Estimation, N=5K', 'MRC, Channel ...
            Estimation, N=50K',...
            'MRC, Channel Estimation, N=10K', 'MRC, Channel Estimation, N=5K')
        axis([-20 0 10^-4 1])
        grid on
        xlabel('SNR (dB)')
        ylabel('Symbol Error Rate per user')
    else
        figure(1)
        semilogy(Parameters.SNR_SER_dB,ResultMonteCarlo.SER_ZF_Full_CSI_Num,'-rs');
        hold on
        semilogy(Parameters.SNR_SER_dB,ResultMonteCarlo.SER_MRC_Full_CSI_Num,'-bs');
```

```

hold on
semilogy(Parameters.SNR_SER_dB,ResultMonteCarlo.SER_ZF_Hest50_Num,'--rs');
hold on
semilogy(Parameters.SNR_SER_dB,ResultMonteCarlo.SER_ZF_Hest10_Num,':rs');
hold on
semilogy(Parameters.SNR_SER_dB,ResultMonteCarlo.SER_ZF_Hest5_Num,'-.rs');
hold on
semilogy(Parameters.SNR_SER_dB,ResultMonteCarlo.SER_MRC_Hest50_Num,'--bs');
hold on
semilogy(Parameters.SNR_SER_dB,ResultMonteCarlo.SER_MRC_Hest10_Num,':bs');
hold on
semilogy(Parameters.SNR_SER_dB,ResultMonteCarlo.SER_MRC_Hest5_Num,'-.bs');
legend('ZF, full CSI','MRC, Full CSI', 'ZF, Channel Estimation, N=50M',...
      'ZF, Channel Estimation, N=10M', 'ZF, Channel Estimation, N=5M', 'MRC, Channel ...
      Estimation, N=50M',...
      'MRC, Channel Estimation, N=10M', 'MRC, Channel Estimation, N=5M')
axis([-20 0 10^-3 1])
grid on
xlabel('SNR (dB)')
ylabel('Symbol Error Rate per user')
end
end

if Parameters.AnalyticalChoice == 1

    if Parameters.ChannelOption == 1

        figure(2)%Plot of Fig.5 Paper
        semilogy(Parameters.SNR_SER_dB,ResultAnalytical.SER_MRC_Analytical(:,1),'-bs');
        hold on
        semilogy(Parameters.SNR_SER_dB,ResultAnalytical.SER_MRC_Analytical(:,2),'--bs');
        hold on
        semilogy(Parameters.SNR_SER_dB,ResultAnalytical.SER_MRC_Analytical(:,3),':bs');
        hold on
        semilogy(Parameters.SNR_SER_dB,ResultAnalytical.SER_MRC_Analytical(:,4),'-.bs');
        legend('ZF, full CSI','MRC, Full CSI', 'ZF, Channel Estimation, N=50K',...
              'ZF, Channel Estimation, N=10K', 'ZF, Channel Estimation, N=5K', 'MRC, Channel ...
              Estimation, N=50K',...
              'MRC, Channel Estimation, N=10K', 'MRC, Channel Estimation, N=5K')
        axis([-20 0 10^-3 1])
        grid on
        xlabel('SNR (dB)')
        ylabel('Symbol Error Rate per user')
    else
        figure(2)
        semilogy(Parameters.SNR_SER_dB,ResultAnalytical.SER_MRC_Analytical(:,1),'-bs');
        hold on
        semilogy(Parameters.SNR_SER_dB,ResultAnalytical.SER_MRC_Analytical(:,2),'--bs');
        hold on
        semilogy(Parameters.SNR_SER_dB,ResultAnalytical.SER_MRC_Analytical(:,3),':bs');
        hold on
        semilogy(Parameters.SNR_SER_dB,ResultAnalytical.SER_MRC_Analytical(:,4),'-.bs');
        legend('ZF, full CSI','MRC, Full CSI', 'ZF, Channel Estimation, N=50M',...
              'ZF, Channel Estimation, N=10M', 'ZF, Channel Estimation, N=5M', 'MRC, Channel ...
              Estimation, N=50M',...
              'MRC, Channel Estimation, N=10M', 'MRC, Channel Estimation, N=5M')
        axis([-20 0 10^-3 1])
        grid on
        xlabel('SNR (dB)')
        ylabel('Symbol Error Rate per user')
    end
end

if Parameters.AnalyticalChoice == 1 && Parameters.MonteCarloChoice == 1
    %figures to compare the analytical approach with the numerical computation

```

```

figure(3)
semilogy(Parameters.SNR_SER_dB,mean(ResultAnalytical.SER_MRC_Analytical(:, :, 1)));
hold on
semilogy(Parameters.SNR_SER_dB,ResultMonteCarlo.SER_MRC_Full_CSI_Num);
xlabel('SNR (dB)')
ylabel('Symbol Error Rate per user')
legend('Analytical','Numerical')
axis([-20 -5 10^-3 1])
end

```

SER Analytical Approach:

```

%%
%We use equation (15) to compute the interferences between users in each antenna
User = 1;%We select a single user which we use to compute the analytical approach
h_ik = H_Full_CSI;
h_ik(:,User) = 0; %it eliminates the user who is not considered interferent
Sigma_I = Parameters.P_tx*sum(abs(h_ik).^2,2);%it is computed the interference noise with the ...
equation (15)
%Probabilities Pic (equations 16-19) for each antenna
Data.P_i1 = zeros(Parameters.M,1);
Data.P_i2 = zeros(Parameters.M,1);
Data.P_i3 = zeros(Parameters.M,1);
Data.P_i4 = zeros(Parameters.M,1);

H_x = H_Full_CSI(:,User);%It is selected the channel for the chosen user
x_k = x(User);%it is selcted the symbol transmitted by the user selecte
for i = 1:Parameters.M %it is compted Pic

Data.P_i1(i) = 0.5*erfc((-sqrt(Parameters.P_tx)*real(H_x(i) * ...
x_k))/(sqrt(n.power+Sigma_I(i))))...
*0.5*erfc((-sqrt(Parameters.P_tx)*imag(H_x(i) * x_k))/(sqrt(n.power+Sigma_I(i))));

Data.P_i2(i) = 0.5*erfc((-sqrt(Parameters.P_tx)*real(H_x(i) * ...
x_k))/(sqrt(n.power+Sigma_I(i))))...
*(1-(0.5*erfc((-sqrt(Parameters.P_tx)*imag(H_x(i) * ...
x_k))/(sqrt(n.power+Sigma_I(i)))))...);

Data.P_i3(i) = (1-(0.5*erfc((-sqrt(Parameters.P_tx)*real(H_x(i) * ...
x_k))/(sqrt(n.power+Sigma_I(i)))))...
*(1-(0.5*erfc((-sqrt(Parameters.P_tx)*imag(H_x(i) * ...
x_k))/(sqrt(n.power+Sigma_I(i)))))...);

Data.P_i4(i) = (1-(0.5*erfc((-sqrt(Parameters.P_tx)*real(H_x(i) * ...
x_k))/(sqrt(n.power+Sigma_I(i)))))...
*0.5*erfc((-sqrt(Parameters.P_tx)*imag(H_x(i) * x_k))/(sqrt(n.power+Sigma_I(i))));

end

A_tot_ZF = cat(3, A_ZF_Full_CSI, A_ZF_HestN50, A_ZF_HestN10, A_ZF_HestN5);%Multidimensional array ...
wich contain all the ZF receive filters
for sel = 1:4%sel is used to select the channels and receive filters within the multidimensional array
H = H_tot(:,User,sel);%it's selected the channel (only for the requiered user)
A = A_tot_ZF(User, :, sel);
%preallocate vectors
Sigma_MRC_tot = zeros(Parameters.M,1);
Mu_MRC_tot = zeros(Parameters.M,1);
Mu_ZF_tot = zeros(Parameters.M,1);
Sigma_ZF_tot = zeros(Parameters.M,1);
for i = 1:Parameters.M%it is computed the Mu and Sigma of the equation (12) for each antenna

Sigma_MRC_tot(i) = (abs(H(i))^2)/(norm(H(:))^4) * (2-(abs(Data.P_i1(i)*Parameters.Symbols(1) + ...
Data.P_i2(i)*Parameters.Symbols(2) + Data.P_i3(i)*Parameters.Symbols(3) + ...

```

```

        Data.P.i4(i)*Parameters.Symbols(4))^2);
    Mu_MRC_tot(i) = (conj(H(i))/(norm(H(:)))^2) * (Data.P.i1(i)*Parameters.Symbols(1) + ...
        Data.P.i2(i)*Parameters.Symbols(2) + Data.P.i3(i)*Parameters.Symbols(3) + ...
        Data.P.i4(i)*Parameters.Symbols(4));
    Sigma_ZF_tot(i) = abs(A(i))^2 * (2-(abs(Data.P.i1(i)*Parameters.Symbols(1) + ...
        Data.P.i2(i)*Parameters.Symbols(2) + Data.P.i3(i)*Parameters.Symbols(3) + ...
        Data.P.i4(i)*Parameters.Symbols(4))^2);
    Mu_ZF_tot(i) = A(i) * (Data.P.i1(i)*Parameters.Symbols(1) + ...
        Data.P.i2(i)*Parameters.Symbols(2) + Data.P.i3(i)*Parameters.Symbols(3) + ...
        Data.P.i4(i)*Parameters.Symbols(4));

end

%The values of Mu and Sigma for each antenna needs to be added in order to
%obtain the PDF showed in (12)
Data.Sigma.l2_MRC = sum(Sigma_MRC_tot);
Data.Sigma.l2_ZF = sum(Sigma_ZF_tot);
Data.Mu.l2_MRC = sum(Mu_MRC_tot);
Data.Mu.l2_ZF = sum(Mu_ZF_tot);
%it is computed the probabilities of estimate each symbol
P1_MRC = qfunc(-real(Data.Mu.l2_MRC)/sqrt(Data.Sigma.l2_MRC/2)) * ...
    qfunc(-imag(Data.Mu.l2_MRC)/sqrt(Data.Sigma.l2_MRC/2)); %con el /2 tenemos en cuenta la parte ...
    real e imaginaria
P2_MRC = qfunc(-real(Data.Mu.l2_MRC)/sqrt(Data.Sigma.l2_MRC/2)) * ...
    (1-qfunc(-imag(Data.Mu.l2_MRC)/sqrt(Data.Sigma.l2_MRC/2)));
P3_MRC = (1-qfunc(-real(Data.Mu.l2_MRC)/sqrt(Data.Sigma.l2_MRC/2))) * ...
    (1-qfunc(-imag(Data.Mu.l2_MRC)/sqrt(Data.Sigma.l2_MRC/2)));
P4_MRC = (1-qfunc(-real(Data.Mu.l2_MRC)/sqrt(Data.Sigma.l2_MRC/2))) * ...
    qfunc(-imag(Data.Mu.l2_MRC)/sqrt(Data.Sigma.l2_MRC/2));
P1_ZF = qfunc(-real(Data.Mu.l2_ZF)/sqrt(Data.Sigma.l2_ZF/2)) * ...
    qfunc(-imag(Data.Mu.l2_ZF)/sqrt(Data.Sigma.l2_ZF/2));
P2_ZF = qfunc(-real(Data.Mu.l2_ZF)/sqrt(Data.Sigma.l2_ZF/2)) * ...
    (1-qfunc(-imag(Data.Mu.l2_ZF)/sqrt(Data.Sigma.l2_ZF/2)));
P3_ZF = (1-qfunc(-real(Data.Mu.l2_ZF)/sqrt(Data.Sigma.l2_ZF/2))) * ...
    (1-qfunc(-imag(Data.Mu.l2_ZF)/sqrt(Data.Sigma.l2_ZF/2)));
P4_ZF = (1-qfunc(-real(Data.Mu.l2_ZF)/sqrt(Data.Sigma.l2_ZF/2))) * ...
    qfunc(-imag(Data.Mu.l2_ZF)/sqrt(Data.Sigma.l2_ZF/2));

Data.P_MRC = [P1_MRC P2_MRC P3_MRC P4_MRC];
Data.P_ZF = [P1_ZF P2_ZF P3_ZF P4_ZF];
P_Xk = 0.25;%QPSK uniformly distributed, 4 symbols all equiprobables
%it is applied equation (23), which we compare the symbol tranmitted by user
%k and it is eliminated the probability (we replace it by 0)
if x.k == (1/sqrt(2))*(1+1j)
    Data.P_MRC(1)=0;
elseif x.k == (1/sqrt(2))*(1-1j)
    Data.P_MRC(2)=0;
elseif x.k == (1/sqrt(2))*(-1-1j)
    Data.P_MRC(3)=0;
elseif x.k == (1/sqrt(2))*(-1+1j)
    Data.P_MRC(4)=0;
end
%now the same but with ZF
if x.k == (1/sqrt(2))*(1+1j)
    Data.P_ZF(1)=0;
elseif x.k == (1/sqrt(2))*(1-1j)
    Data.P_ZF(2)=0;
elseif x.k == (1/sqrt(2))*(-1-1j)
    Data.P_ZF(3)=0;
elseif x.k == (1/sqrt(2))*(-1+1j)
    Data.P_ZF(4)=0;
end

%it is applied equation (23)
ResultAnalytical.SER_MRC_Analytical(Sim,Pot,sel) = 4*sum(Data.P_MRC*P_Xk);

```

```

ResultAnalytical.SER.ZF.Analytical(Sim,Pot,sel) = 4*sum(Data.P.ZF*P.Xk);

assignin('base','Data',Data)
end

```

Mutual Information for Random Channel:

```

for Pot = 1:length(Parameters.NoisePowerMI)%Choose the power from vector NoisePowerSER

    n_power = Parameters.NoisePowerMI(Pot);%Selected noise to simulate with

    for Sim = 1:Parameters.Simulations%Number of Monte Carlo Simulations of the channel matrix
        %Random Channel Matrix generation
        H.Full.CSI = ...
            (1/sqrt(2))*(randn(Parameters.M,Parameters.K)+1j*randn(Parameters.M,Parameters.K));%function ...
            that estimate the channel using 3 different training lengths
        [Hest.N50, Hest.N10, Hest.N5] = Channel.H.Estimation(H.Full.CSI, n_power, ...
            Parameters);%Channel Matrix estimated
        H.tot = cat(3, H.Full.CSI, Hest.N50, Hest.N10, Hest.N5);%Multidimensional matrix with all ...
            the channel matrix

        %% ...
        -----
        [A.ZF.Full.CSI, A.MRC.Full.CSI, A.ZF.HestN50, A.ZF.HestN10, A.ZF.HestN5,...
        A.MRC.HestN50, A.MRC.HestN10, A.MRC.HestN5] = ...
            Estimation.Filters(H.tot, Parameters); %Function wich compute the ZF and MRC receive ...
            filters

        %% ...
        -----
        s1.MRC.Full.CSI=0;s2.MRC.Full.CSI=0;s3.MRC.Full.CSI=0;s4.MRC.Full.CSI=0;%it resets the ...
            number of estimations in each channel simulation
        s1.ZF.Full.CSI=0 ; s2.ZF.Full.CSI=0 ; s3.ZF.Full.CSI=0 ; s4.ZF.Full.CSI=0;
        s1.MRC.HestN50=0 ; s2.MRC.HestN50=0 ; s3.MRC.HestN50=0 ; s4.MRC.HestN50=0;
        s1.MRC.HestN10=0 ; s2.MRC.HestN10=0 ; s3.MRC.HestN10=0 ; s4.MRC.HestN10=0;
        s1.MRC.HestN5=0 ; s2.MRC.HestN5=0 ; s3.MRC.HestN5=0 ; s4.MRC.HestN5=0;
        s1.ZF.HestN50=0 ; s2.ZF.HestN50=0 ; s3.ZF.HestN50=0 ; s4.ZF.HestN50=0;
        s1.ZF.HestN10=0 ; s2.ZF.HestN10=0 ; s3.ZF.HestN10=0 ; s4.ZF.HestN10=0;
        s1.ZF.HestN5=0 ; s2.ZF.HestN5=0 ; s3.ZF.HestN5=0 ; s4.ZF.HestN5=0;

        for Sim2 = 1:Parameters.Simulations%Number of Monte Carlo Simulations of 'n' and 'x'

            User=1;% chosen user needed to compute the Mutual information
            x = ones(Parameters.K,1);
            for i = 1:Parameters.K %symbol generation of the K users
                j = randi(4);%selector of symbol to transmit
                x(i)= Parameters.QPSK(j);
                x(User)= Parameters.QPSK(1);%The chosen user always needs to send the same ...
                    symbol, in that case 1+j
            end

            n = sqrt(n_power / 2) * (randn(Parameters.M,1)+1j*randn(Parameters.M,1));%Complex ...
                gaussian noise.
            r = sqrt(Parameters.P.tx)*H.Full.CSI*x+n;%Discrete-time complex baseband received ...
                signal at the base station (Eq.1)
            y = sign(real(r))+1j*sign(imag(r));%quantizer

            %% ...
            -----

            %It is estimated only the symbol transmitted by the selected user
            x.est.ZF.Full.CSI = A.ZF.Full.CSI(User,:) * y;%Soft estimate of the transmitted symbols ...
                with A.ZF (Eq.3)
            x.est.MRC.Full.CSI = A.MRC.Full.CSI(:,User)' * y;%Soft estimate of the transmitted ...
                symbols with A.MRC (Eq.3), we need to do the Hermitian
            x.est.ZF.HestN50 = A.ZF.HestN50(User,:) * y;
            x.est.ZF.HestN10 = A.ZF.HestN10(User,:) * y;
            x.est.ZF.HestN5 = A.ZF.HestN5(User,:) * y;

```

```

x_est_MRC_HestN50 = A_MRC_HestN50(:,User)' * y;
x_est_MRC_HestN10 = A_MRC_HestN10(:,User)' * y;
x_est_MRC_HestN5 = A_MRC_HestN5(:,User)' * y;
%% ...
-----
%Decisor
x_est_ZF_decis_Full_CSI = ...
    ((1/sqrt(2))*(sign(real(x_est_ZF_Full_CSI))+1j*sign(imag(x_est_ZF_Full_CSI))));
x_est_MRC_decis_Full_CSI = ...
    ((1/sqrt(2))*(sign(real(x_est_MRC_Full_CSI))+1j*sign(imag(x_est_MRC_Full_CSI))));
x_est_ZF_decis_HestN50 = ...
    (1/sqrt(2))*(sign(real(x_est_ZF_HestN50))+1j*sign(imag(x_est_ZF_HestN50)));
x_est_ZF_decis_HestN10 = ...
    (1/sqrt(2))*(sign(real(x_est_ZF_HestN10))+1j*sign(imag(x_est_ZF_HestN10)));
x_est_ZF_decis_HestN5 = ...
    (1/sqrt(2))*(sign(real(x_est_ZF_HestN5))+1j*sign(imag(x_est_ZF_HestN5)));
x_est_MRC_decis_HestN50 = ...
    (1/sqrt(2))*(sign(real(x_est_MRC_HestN50))+1j*sign(imag(x_est_MRC_HestN50)));
x_est_MRC_decis_HestN10 = ...
    (1/sqrt(2))*(sign(real(x_est_MRC_HestN10))+1j*sign(imag(x_est_MRC_HestN10)));
x_est_MRC_decis_HestN5 = ...
    (1/sqrt(2))*(sign(real(x_est_MRC_HestN5))+1j*sign(imag(x_est_MRC_HestN5)));
%% ...
-----
%It is computed the number of symbols estimated in each case by
%all the simulations of 'x' and 'n'
%MRC FullCSI
if x_est_MRC_decis_Full_CSI == 1/sqrt(2)*(1+1j)
    s1_MRC_Full_CSI = s1_MRC_Full_CSI+1;
elseif x_est_MRC_decis_Full_CSI == 1/sqrt(2)*(1-1j)
    s2_MRC_Full_CSI = s2_MRC_Full_CSI+1;
elseif x_est_MRC_decis_Full_CSI == 1/sqrt(2)*(-1-1j)
    s3_MRC_Full_CSI = s3_MRC_Full_CSI+1;
elseif x_est_MRC_decis_Full_CSI == 1/sqrt(2)*(-1+1j)
    s4_MRC_Full_CSI = s4_MRC_Full_CSI+1;
end
%ZF FullCSI
if x_est_ZF_decis_Full_CSI == 1/sqrt(2)*(1+1j)
    s1_ZF_Full_CSI = s1_ZF_Full_CSI+1;
elseif x_est_ZF_decis_Full_CSI == 1/sqrt(2)*(1-1j)
    s2_ZF_Full_CSI = s2_ZF_Full_CSI+1;
elseif x_est_ZF_decis_Full_CSI == 1/sqrt(2)*(-1-1j)
    s3_ZF_Full_CSI = s3_ZF_Full_CSI+1;
elseif x_est_ZF_decis_Full_CSI == 1/sqrt(2)*(-1+1j)
    s4_ZF_Full_CSI = s4_ZF_Full_CSI+1;
end
%MRC Hest 50
if x_est_MRC_decis_HestN50 == 1/sqrt(2)*(1+1j)
    s1_MRC_HestN50 = s1_MRC_HestN50+1;
elseif x_est_MRC_decis_HestN50 == 1/sqrt(2)*(1-1j)
    s2_MRC_HestN50 = s2_MRC_HestN50+1;
elseif x_est_MRC_decis_HestN50 == 1/sqrt(2)*(-1-1j)
    s3_MRC_HestN50 = s3_MRC_HestN50+1;
elseif x_est_MRC_decis_HestN50 == 1/sqrt(2)*(-1+1j)
    s4_MRC_HestN50 = s4_MRC_HestN50+1;
end
%MRC Hest10
if x_est_MRC_decis_HestN10 == 1/sqrt(2)*(1+1j)
    s1_MRC_HestN10 = s1_MRC_HestN10+1;
elseif x_est_MRC_decis_HestN10 == 1/sqrt(2)*(1-1j)
    s2_MRC_HestN10 = s2_MRC_HestN10+1;
elseif x_est_MRC_decis_HestN10 == 1/sqrt(2)*(-1-1j)
    s3_MRC_HestN10 = s3_MRC_HestN10+1;
elseif x_est_MRC_decis_HestN10 == 1/sqrt(2)*(-1+1j)
    s4_MRC_HestN10 = s4_MRC_HestN10+1;

```

```

end
%MRC Hest5
if x.est_MRC.decis_HestN5 == 1/sqrt(2)*(1+1j)
    s1_MRC.HestN5 = s1_MRC.HestN5+1;
elseif x.est_MRC.decis_HestN5 == 1/sqrt(2)*(1-1j)
    s2_MRC.HestN5 = s2_MRC.HestN5+1;
elseif x.est_MRC.decis_HestN5 == 1/sqrt(2)*(-1-1j)
    s3_MRC.HestN5 = s3_MRC.HestN5+1;
elseif x.est_MRC.decis_HestN5 == 1/sqrt(2)*(-1+1j)
    s4_MRC.HestN5 = s4_MRC.HestN5+1;
end
%ZF Hest 50
if x.est_ZF.decis_HestN50 == 1/sqrt(2)*(1+1j)
    s1_ZF.HestN50 = s1_ZF.HestN50+1;
elseif x.est_ZF.decis_HestN50 == 1/sqrt(2)*(1-1j)
    s2_ZF.HestN50 = s2_ZF.HestN50+1;
elseif x.est_ZF.decis_HestN50 == 1/sqrt(2)*(-1-1j)
    s3_ZF.HestN50 = s3_ZF.HestN50+1;
elseif x.est_ZF.decis_HestN50 == 1/sqrt(2)*(-1+1j)
    s4_ZF.HestN50 = s4_ZF.HestN50+1;
end
%ZF Hest10
if x.est_ZF.decis_HestN10 == 1/sqrt(2)*(1+1j)
    s1_ZF.HestN10 = s1_ZF.HestN10+1;
elseif x.est_ZF.decis_HestN10 == 1/sqrt(2)*(1-1j)
    s2_ZF.HestN10 = s2_ZF.HestN10+1;
elseif x.est_ZF.decis_HestN10 == 1/sqrt(2)*(-1-1j)
    s3_ZF.HestN10 = s3_ZF.HestN10+1;
elseif x.est_ZF.decis_HestN10 == 1/sqrt(2)*(-1+1j)
    s4_ZF.HestN10 = s4_ZF.HestN10+1;
end
%ZF Hest5
if x.est_ZF.decis_HestN5 == 1/sqrt(2)*(1+1j)
    s1_ZF.HestN5 = s1_ZF.HestN5+1;
elseif x.est_ZF.decis_HestN5 == 1/sqrt(2)*(1-1j)
    s2_ZF.HestN5 = s2_ZF.HestN5+1;
elseif x.est_ZF.decis_HestN5 == 1/sqrt(2)*(-1-1j)
    s3_ZF.HestN5 = s3_ZF.HestN5+1;
elseif x.est_ZF.decis_HestN5 == 1/sqrt(2)*(-1+1j)
    s4_ZF.HestN5 = s4_ZF.HestN5+1;
end
%% ...
-----
%Only is executed if Analytical approach procedure is selected
if Parameters.AnalyticalChoice == 1
    AnalyticalApproachMI
end
end
%% ...
-----
%It is computed the average number of estimations of each symbol in the x's and 'n' simulations
%MRC Full CSI
s1_tot_MRC.Full_CSI(Sim,Pot) = s1_MRC.Full_CSI/Parameters.Simulations;
s2_tot_MRC.Full_CSI(Sim,Pot) = s2_MRC.Full_CSI/Parameters.Simulations;
s3_tot_MRC.Full_CSI(Sim,Pot) = s3_MRC.Full_CSI/Parameters.Simulations;
s4_tot_MRC.Full_CSI(Sim,Pot) = s4_MRC.Full_CSI/Parameters.Simulations;
%ZF Full CSI
s1_tot_ZF.Full_CSI(Sim,Pot) = s1_ZF.Full_CSI/Parameters.Simulations;
s2_tot_ZF.Full_CSI(Sim,Pot) = s2_ZF.Full_CSI/Parameters.Simulations;
s3_tot_ZF.Full_CSI(Sim,Pot) = s3_ZF.Full_CSI/Parameters.Simulations;
s4_tot_ZF.Full_CSI(Sim,Pot) = s4_ZF.Full_CSI/Parameters.Simulations;
%MRC Hest50
s1_tot_MRC.HestN50(Sim,Pot) = s1_MRC.HestN50/Parameters.Simulations;
s2_tot_MRC.HestN50(Sim,Pot) = s2_MRC.HestN50/Parameters.Simulations;
s3_tot_MRC.HestN50(Sim,Pot) = s3_MRC.HestN50/Parameters.Simulations;

```

```

s4_tot_MRC_HestN50(Sim,Pot) = s4_MRC_HestN50/Parameters.Simulations;
%MRC Hest10
s1_tot_MRC_HestN10(Sim,Pot) = s1_MRC_HestN10/Parameters.Simulations;
s2_tot_MRC_HestN10(Sim,Pot) = s2_MRC_HestN10/Parameters.Simulations;
s3_tot_MRC_HestN10(Sim,Pot) = s3_MRC_HestN10/Parameters.Simulations;
s4_tot_MRC_HestN10(Sim,Pot) = s4_MRC_HestN10/Parameters.Simulations;
%MRC Hest5
s1_tot_MRC_HestN5(Sim,Pot) = s1_MRC_HestN5/Parameters.Simulations;
s2_tot_MRC_HestN5(Sim,Pot) = s2_MRC_HestN5/Parameters.Simulations;
s3_tot_MRC_HestN5(Sim,Pot) = s3_MRC_HestN5/Parameters.Simulations;
s4_tot_MRC_HestN5(Sim,Pot) = s4_MRC_HestN5/Parameters.Simulations;
%ZF Hest50
s1_tot_ZF_HestN50(Sim,Pot) = s1_ZF_HestN50/Parameters.Simulations;
s2_tot_ZF_HestN50(Sim,Pot) = s2_ZF_HestN50/Parameters.Simulations;
s3_tot_ZF_HestN50(Sim,Pot) = s3_ZF_HestN50/Parameters.Simulations;
s4_tot_ZF_HestN50(Sim,Pot) = s4_ZF_HestN50/Parameters.Simulations;
%ZF Hest10
s1_tot_ZF_HestN10(Sim,Pot) = s1_ZF_HestN10/Parameters.Simulations;
s2_tot_ZF_HestN10(Sim,Pot) = s2_ZF_HestN10/Parameters.Simulations;
s3_tot_ZF_HestN10(Sim,Pot) = s3_ZF_HestN10/Parameters.Simulations;
s4_tot_ZF_HestN10(Sim,Pot) = s4_ZF_HestN10/Parameters.Simulations;
%ZF Hest50
s1_tot_ZF_HestN5(Sim,Pot) = s1_ZF_HestN5/Parameters.Simulations;
s2_tot_ZF_HestN5(Sim,Pot) = s2_ZF_HestN5/Parameters.Simulations;
s3_tot_ZF_HestN5(Sim,Pot) = s3_ZF_HestN5/Parameters.Simulations;
s4_tot_ZF_HestN5(Sim,Pot) = s4_ZF_HestN5/Parameters.Simulations;
end
end
%% ...
-----
%Only is executed if Analytical approach procedure is selected
if Parameters.AnalyticalChoice == 1
    ResultAnalytical.MutualInfoMRC = mean(DataAnalytical.MutualInfoMRC_tot);
    ResultAnalytical.MutualInfoZF = mean(DataAnalytical.MutualInfoZF_tot);
    assignin('base', 'ResultAnalytical', ResultAnalytical)
end
%% ...
-----
%The ratio of symbols estimated of each channel simulation is averaged
P1_MRC_Full_CSI = mean(s1_tot_MRC_Full_CSI);
P2_MRC_Full_CSI = mean(s2_tot_MRC_Full_CSI);
P3_MRC_Full_CSI = mean(s3_tot_MRC_Full_CSI);
P4_MRC_Full_CSI = mean(s4_tot_MRC_Full_CSI);

P1_ZF_Full_CSI = mean(s1_tot_ZF_Full_CSI);
P2_ZF_Full_CSI = mean(s2_tot_ZF_Full_CSI);
P3_ZF_Full_CSI = mean(s3_tot_ZF_Full_CSI);
P4_ZF_Full_CSI = mean(s4_tot_ZF_Full_CSI);

P1_MRC_HestN50 = mean(s1_tot_MRC_HestN50);
P2_MRC_HestN50 = mean(s2_tot_MRC_HestN50);
P3_MRC_HestN50 = mean(s3_tot_MRC_HestN50);
P4_MRC_HestN50 = mean(s4_tot_MRC_HestN50);

P1_MRC_HestN10 = mean(s1_tot_MRC_HestN10);
P2_MRC_HestN10 = mean(s2_tot_MRC_HestN10);
P3_MRC_HestN10 = mean(s3_tot_MRC_HestN10);
P4_MRC_HestN10 = mean(s4_tot_MRC_HestN10);

P1_MRC_HestN5 = mean(s1_tot_MRC_HestN5);
P2_MRC_HestN5 = mean(s2_tot_MRC_HestN5);
P3_MRC_HestN5 = mean(s3_tot_MRC_HestN5);
P4_MRC_HestN5 = mean(s4_tot_MRC_HestN5);

P1_ZF_HestN50 = mean(s1_tot_ZF_HestN50);

```

```

P2_ZF_HestN50 = mean(s2_tot_ZF_HestN50);
P3_ZF_HestN50 = mean(s3_tot_ZF_HestN50);
P4_ZF_HestN50 = mean(s4_tot_ZF_HestN50);

P1_ZF_HestN10 = mean(s1_tot_ZF_HestN10);
P2_ZF_HestN10 = mean(s2_tot_ZF_HestN10);
P3_ZF_HestN10 = mean(s3_tot_ZF_HestN10);
P4_ZF_HestN10 = mean(s4_tot_ZF_HestN10);

P1_ZF_HestN5 = mean(s1_tot_ZF_HestN5);
P2_ZF_HestN5 = mean(s2_tot_ZF_HestN5);
P3_ZF_HestN5 = mean(s3_tot_ZF_HestN5);
P4_ZF_HestN5 = mean(s4_tot_ZF_HestN5);
%% ...
-----
P_Xk=0.25; %qpsk equally distributed
%%
P_MRC_Full_CSI = [P1_MRC_Full_CSI; P2_MRC_Full_CSI; P3_MRC_Full_CSI; P4_MRC_Full_CSI];
P_ZF_Full_CSI = [P1_ZF_Full_CSI; P2_ZF_Full_CSI; P3_ZF_Full_CSI; P4_ZF_Full_CSI];
P_MRC_HestN50 = [P1_MRC_HestN50; P2_MRC_HestN50; P3_MRC_HestN50; P4_MRC_HestN50];
P_MRC_HestN10 = [P1_MRC_HestN10; P2_MRC_HestN10; P3_MRC_HestN10; P4_MRC_HestN10];
P_MRC_HestN5 = [P1_MRC_HestN5; P2_MRC_HestN5; P3_MRC_HestN5; P4_MRC_HestN5];
P_ZF_HestN50 = [P1_ZF_HestN50; P2_ZF_HestN50; P3_ZF_HestN50; P4_ZF_HestN50];
P_ZF_HestN10 = [P1_ZF_HestN10; P2_ZF_HestN10; P3_ZF_HestN10; P4_ZF_HestN10];
P_ZF_HestN5 = [P1_ZF_HestN5; P2_ZF_HestN5; P3_ZF_HestN5; P4_ZF_HestN5];
%%preallocation for speed
MI_MRC_Full_CSI = zeros(length(Parameters.NoisePowerMI),1);
MI_ZF_Full_CSI = zeros(length(Parameters.NoisePowerMI),1);
MI_MRC_HestN50 = zeros(length(Parameters.NoisePowerMI),1);
MI_MRC_HestN10 = zeros(length(Parameters.NoisePowerMI),1);
MI_MRC_HestN5 = zeros(length(Parameters.NoisePowerMI),1);
MI_ZF_HestN50 = zeros(length(Parameters.NoisePowerMI),1);
MI_ZF_HestN10 = zeros(length(Parameters.NoisePowerMI),1);
MI_ZF_HestN5 = zeros(length(Parameters.NoisePowerMI),1);
%% ...
-----
%Mutual information computation using equation (10) and Monte Carlo simulations
for i=1:length(Parameters.NoisePowerMI)

    ResultMonteCarlo.MI_MRC_Full_CSI(i) = ...
        4*sum(P_MRC_Full_CSI(:,i)*P_Xk.*(log2(P_MRC_Full_CSI(:,i)/sum(P_MRC_Full_CSI(:,i)*P_Xk))));
    ResultMonteCarlo.MI_ZF_Full_CSI(i) = ...
        4*sum(P_ZF_Full_CSI(:,i)*P_Xk.*(log2(P_ZF_Full_CSI(:,i)/sum(P_ZF_Full_CSI(:,i)*P_Xk))));
    ResultMonteCarlo.MI_MRC_HestN50(i) = ...
        4*sum(P_MRC_HestN50(:,i)*P_Xk.*(log2(P_MRC_HestN50(:,i)/sum(P_MRC_HestN50(:,i)*P_Xk))));
    ResultMonteCarlo.MI_MRC_HestN10(i) = ...
        4*sum(P_MRC_HestN10(:,i)*P_Xk.*(log2(P_MRC_HestN10(:,i)/sum(P_MRC_HestN10(:,i)*P_Xk))));
    ResultMonteCarlo.MI_MRC_HestN5(i) = ...
        4*sum(P_MRC_HestN5(:,i)*P_Xk.*(log2(P_MRC_HestN5(:,i)/sum(P_MRC_HestN5(:,i)*P_Xk))));
    ResultMonteCarlo.MI_ZF_HestN50(i) = ...
        4*sum(P_ZF_HestN50(:,i)*P_Xk.*(log2(P_ZF_HestN50(:,i)/sum(P_ZF_HestN50(:,i)*P_Xk))));
    ResultMonteCarlo.MI_ZF_HestN10(i) = ...
        4*sum(P_ZF_HestN10(:,i)*P_Xk.*(log2(P_ZF_HestN10(:,i)/sum(P_ZF_HestN10(:,i)*P_Xk))));
    ResultMonteCarlo.MI_ZF_HestN5(i) = ...
        4*sum(P_ZF_HestN5(:,i)*P_Xk.*(log2(P_ZF_HestN5(:,i)/sum(P_ZF_HestN5(:,i)*P_Xk))));
end
assignin('base','Result',ResultMonteCarlo)
%plot
Plot_MI

```

Mutual Information for MmWave Channel with Beamforming:

```

for Pot = 1:length(Parameters.NoisePowerMI)%Choose the power from vector NoisePowerSER

    n.power = Parameters.NoisePowerMI(Pot);%Selected noise to simulate with

    for Sim = 1:Parameters.Simulations%Number of Monte Carlo Simulations of the channel matrix

        [H_mmWave_Full_CSI, Cluster_Center_deg_tot] = mmWave_Channel(Parameters);%Mmwave Channel ...
        Model generation
        H_Full_CSI = H_mmWave_Full_CSI;
        [Hest_N50, Hest_N10, Hest_N5] = Channel_H_Estimation(H_mmWave_Full_CSI, n.power, ...
        Parameters);%Channel Matrix estimated
    %% ...
    -----
        H_tot = cat(3, H_mmWave_Full_CSI, Hest_N50, Hest_N10, Hest_N5);%Multidimensional matrix with ...
        all the channel matrix
    %% ...
    -----
        [B, H_Effective, D] = Beamforming(Parameters,H_tot,Cluster_Center_deg_tot);%Function that ...
        compute the beamers and the parameters of the beamforming
    %% ...
    -----
        [A_ZF_Full_CSI, A_MRC_Full_CSI, A_ZF_HestN50, A_ZF_HestN10, A_ZF_HestN5,...
        A_MRC_HestN50, A_MRC_HestN10, A_MRC_HestN5] = ...
        Estimation_Filters_Beamforming(H_Effective, D, Parameters); %Function wich compute the ...
        ZF and MRC receive filters
    %% ...
    -----
        s1_MRC_Full_CSI=0;s2_MRC_Full_CSI=0;s3_MRC_Full_CSI=0;s4_MRC_Full_CSI=0;%it resets the ...
        number of estimations in each channel simulation
        s1_ZF_Full_CSI=0 ;s2_ZF_Full_CSI=0 ;s3_ZF_Full_CSI=0 ;s4_ZF_Full_CSI=0;
        s1_MRC_HestN50=0 ;s2_MRC_HestN50=0 ;s3_MRC_HestN50=0 ;s4_MRC_HestN50=0;
        s1_MRC_HestN10=0 ;s2_MRC_HestN10=0 ;s3_MRC_HestN10=0 ;s4_MRC_HestN10=0;
        s1_MRC_HestN5=0 ;s2_MRC_HestN5=0 ;s3_MRC_HestN5=0 ;s4_MRC_HestN5=0;
        s1_ZF_HestN50=0 ;s2_ZF_HestN50=0 ;s3_ZF_HestN50=0 ;s4_ZF_HestN50=0;
        s1_ZF_HestN10=0 ;s2_ZF_HestN10=0 ;s3_ZF_HestN10=0 ;s4_ZF_HestN10=0;
        s1_ZF_HestN5=0 ;s2_ZF_HestN5=0 ;s3_ZF_HestN5=0 ;s4_ZF_HestN5=0;
        for Sim2 = 1:Parameters.Simulations%Number of Monte Carlo Simulations of 'n' and 'x'

            User=1;% chosen user needed to compute the Mutual information
            x = ones(Parameters.K,1);
            for i = 1:Parameters.K %symbol generation of the K users
                j = randi(4);%selector of symbol to tranmsit
                x(i)= Parameters.QPSK(j);
                x(User)= Parameters.QPSK(1);%The chosen user always needs to send the same ...
                symbol, in that case 1+j
            end
            n = sqrt(n.power / 2) * (randn(Parameters.M,1)+lj*randn(Parameters.M,1));%Complex ...
            gaussian noise.
            for Sel=1:4%selector of the four beamforming matrix

                r = sqrt(Parameters.P_tx)*H_mmWave_Full_CSI*x+n;%Discrete-time complex baseband ...
                received signal at the base station (Eq.1)
                r_Q = B(:, :, Sel)*r;
                y(:, Sel) = sign(real(r_Q))+lj*sign(imag(r_Q));

            end
        %% ...
    -----
        %It is estimated only the symbol tranmsited by the selected user
        x_est_ZF_Full_CSI = A_ZF_Full_CSI(User, :) * y;%Soft estimate of the transmitted symbols ...
        with A_ZF (Eq.3)
    
```

```

x_est_MRC_Full_CSI = A_MRC_Full_CSI(:,User)' * y;%Soft estimate of the transmitted ...
    symbols with A_MRC (Eq.3), we need to do the Hermitian
x_est_ZF_HestN50 = A_ZF_HestN50(User,:) * y;
x_est_ZF_HestN10 = A_ZF_HestN10(User,:) * y;
x_est_ZF_HestN5 = A_ZF_HestN5(User,:) * y;
x_est_MRC_HestN50 = A_MRC_HestN50(:,User)' * y;
x_est_MRC_HestN10 = A_MRC_HestN10(:,User)' * y;
x_est_MRC_HestN5 = A_MRC_HestN5(:,User)' * y;

%% ...

-----

%Decisor
x_est_ZF_decis_Full_CSI = ...
    (1/sqrt(2))*(sign(real(x_est_ZF_Full_CSI))+1j*sign(imag(x_est_ZF_Full_CSI)));
x_est_MRC_decis_Full_CSI = ...
    (1/sqrt(2))*(sign(real(x_est_MRC_Full_CSI))+1j*sign(imag(x_est_MRC_Full_CSI)));
x_est_ZF_decis_HestN50 = ...
    (1/sqrt(2))*(sign(real(x_est_ZF_HestN50))+1j*sign(imag(x_est_ZF_HestN50)));
x_est_ZF_decis_HestN10 = ...
    (1/sqrt(2))*(sign(real(x_est_ZF_HestN10))+1j*sign(imag(x_est_ZF_HestN10)));
x_est_ZF_decis_HestN5 = ...
    (1/sqrt(2))*(sign(real(x_est_ZF_HestN5))+1j*sign(imag(x_est_ZF_HestN5)));
x_est_MRC_decis_HestN50 = ...
    (1/sqrt(2))*(sign(real(x_est_MRC_HestN50))+1j*sign(imag(x_est_MRC_HestN50)));
x_est_MRC_decis_HestN10 = ...
    (1/sqrt(2))*(sign(real(x_est_MRC_HestN10))+1j*sign(imag(x_est_MRC_HestN10)));
x_est_MRC_decis_HestN5 = ...
    (1/sqrt(2))*(sign(real(x_est_MRC_HestN5))+1j*sign(imag(x_est_MRC_HestN5)));

%% ...

-----

%It is computed the number of symbols estimated in each case by
%all the simulations of 'x' and 'n'
%MRC FullCSI
if x_est_MRC_decis_Full_CSI == 1/sqrt(2)*(1+1j)
    s1_MRC_Full_CSI = s1_MRC_Full_CSI+1;
elseif x_est_MRC_decis_Full_CSI == 1/sqrt(2)*(1-1j)
    s2_MRC_Full_CSI = s2_MRC_Full_CSI+1;
elseif x_est_MRC_decis_Full_CSI == 1/sqrt(2)*(-1-1j)
    s3_MRC_Full_CSI = s3_MRC_Full_CSI+1;
elseif x_est_MRC_decis_Full_CSI == 1/sqrt(2)*(-1+1j)
    s4_MRC_Full_CSI = s4_MRC_Full_CSI+1;
end
%ZF FullCSI
if x_est_ZF_decis_Full_CSI == 1/sqrt(2)*(1+1j)
    s1_ZF_Full_CSI = s1_ZF_Full_CSI+1;
elseif x_est_ZF_decis_Full_CSI == 1/sqrt(2)*(1-1j)
    s2_ZF_Full_CSI = s2_ZF_Full_CSI+1;
elseif x_est_ZF_decis_Full_CSI == 1/sqrt(2)*(-1-1j)
    s3_ZF_Full_CSI = s3_ZF_Full_CSI+1;
elseif x_est_ZF_decis_Full_CSI == 1/sqrt(2)*(-1+1j)
    s4_ZF_Full_CSI = s4_ZF_Full_CSI+1;
end
%MRC Hest 50
if x_est_MRC_decis_HestN50 == 1/sqrt(2)*(1+1j)
    s1_MRC_HestN50 = s1_MRC_HestN50+1;
elseif x_est_MRC_decis_HestN50 == 1/sqrt(2)*(1-1j)
    s2_MRC_HestN50 = s2_MRC_HestN50+1;
elseif x_est_MRC_decis_HestN50 == 1/sqrt(2)*(-1-1j)
    s3_MRC_HestN50 = s3_MRC_HestN50+1;
elseif x_est_MRC_decis_HestN50 == 1/sqrt(2)*(-1+1j)
    s4_MRC_HestN50 = s4_MRC_HestN50+1;
end
%MRC Hest10
if x_est_MRC_decis_HestN10 == 1/sqrt(2)*(1+1j)
    s1_MRC_HestN10 = s1_MRC_HestN10+1;
elseif x_est_MRC_decis_HestN10 == 1/sqrt(2)*(1-1j)

```

```

        s2_MRC_HestN10 = s2_MRC_HestN10+1;
    elseif x_est_MRC_decis_HestN10 == 1/sqrt(2)*(-1-1j)
        s3_MRC_HestN10 = s3_MRC_HestN10+1;
    elseif x_est_MRC_decis_HestN10 == 1/sqrt(2)*(-1+1j)
        s4_MRC_HestN10 = s4_MRC_HestN10+1;
    end
    %MRC Hest5
    if x_est_MRC_decis_HestN5 == 1/sqrt(2)*(1+1j)
        s1_MRC_HestN5 = s1_MRC_HestN5+1;
    elseif x_est_MRC_decis_HestN5 == 1/sqrt(2)*(1-1j)
        s2_MRC_HestN5 = s2_MRC_HestN5+1;
    elseif x_est_MRC_decis_HestN5 == 1/sqrt(2)*(-1-1j)
        s3_MRC_HestN5 = s3_MRC_HestN5+1;
    elseif x_est_MRC_decis_HestN5 == 1/sqrt(2)*(-1+1j)
        s4_MRC_HestN5 = s4_MRC_HestN5+1;
    end
    %ZF Hest 50
    if x_est_ZF_decis_HestN50 == 1/sqrt(2)*(1+1j)
        s1_ZF_HestN50 = s1_ZF_HestN50+1;
    elseif x_est_ZF_decis_HestN50 == 1/sqrt(2)*(1-1j)
        s2_ZF_HestN50 = s2_ZF_HestN50+1;
    elseif x_est_ZF_decis_HestN50 == 1/sqrt(2)*(-1-1j)
        s3_ZF_HestN50 = s3_ZF_HestN50+1;
    elseif x_est_ZF_decis_HestN50 == 1/sqrt(2)*(-1+1j)
        s4_ZF_HestN50 = s4_ZF_HestN50+1;
    end
    %ZF Hest10
    if x_est_ZF_decis_HestN10 == 1/sqrt(2)*(1+1j)
        s1_ZF_HestN10 = s1_ZF_HestN10+1;
    elseif x_est_ZF_decis_HestN10 == 1/sqrt(2)*(1-1j)
        s2_ZF_HestN10 = s2_ZF_HestN10+1;
    elseif x_est_ZF_decis_HestN10 == 1/sqrt(2)*(-1-1j)
        s3_ZF_HestN10 = s3_ZF_HestN10+1;
    elseif x_est_ZF_decis_HestN10 == 1/sqrt(2)*(-1+1j)
        s4_ZF_HestN10 = s4_ZF_HestN10+1;
    end
    %ZF Hest5
    if x_est_ZF_decis_HestN5 == 1/sqrt(2)*(1+1j)
        s1_ZF_HestN5 = s1_ZF_HestN5+1;
    elseif x_est_ZF_decis_HestN5 == 1/sqrt(2)*(1-1j)
        s2_ZF_HestN5 = s2_ZF_HestN5+1;
    elseif x_est_ZF_decis_HestN5 == 1/sqrt(2)*(-1-1j)
        s3_ZF_HestN5 = s3_ZF_HestN5+1;
    elseif x_est_ZF_decis_HestN5 == 1/sqrt(2)*(-1+1j)
        s4_ZF_HestN5 = s4_ZF_HestN5+1;
    end
end
%% ...

-----
%Only is executed if Analytical approach procedure is selected
if Parameters.AnalyticalChoice == 1
    AnalyticalApproach.Beamforming_MI
end
%% ...

-----
%It is computed the average number of estimations of each symbol in the 'x' and 'n' simulations
%MRC Full CSI
s1_tot_MRC_Full_CSI(Sim,Pot) = s1_MRC_Full_CSI/Parameters.Simulations;
s2_tot_MRC_Full_CSI(Sim,Pot) = s2_MRC_Full_CSI/Parameters.Simulations;
s3_tot_MRC_Full_CSI(Sim,Pot) = s3_MRC_Full_CSI/Parameters.Simulations;
s4_tot_MRC_Full_CSI(Sim,Pot) = s4_MRC_Full_CSI/Parameters.Simulations;
%ZF Full CSI
s1_tot_ZF_Full_CSI(Sim,Pot) = s1_ZF_Full_CSI/Parameters.Simulations;
s2_tot_ZF_Full_CSI(Sim,Pot) = s2_ZF_Full_CSI/Parameters.Simulations;
s3_tot_ZF_Full_CSI(Sim,Pot) = s3_ZF_Full_CSI/Parameters.Simulations;

```

```

s4_tot_ZF_Full_CSI (Sim,Pot) = s4_ZF_Full_CSI/Parameters.Simulations;
%MRC Hest50
s1_tot_MRC_HestN50 (Sim,Pot) = s1_MRC_HestN50/Parameters.Simulations;
s2_tot_MRC_HestN50 (Sim,Pot) = s2_MRC_HestN50/Parameters.Simulations;
s3_tot_MRC_HestN50 (Sim,Pot) = s3_MRC_HestN50/Parameters.Simulations;
s4_tot_MRC_HestN50 (Sim,Pot) = s4_MRC_HestN50/Parameters.Simulations;
%MRC Hest10
s1_tot_MRC_HestN10 (Sim,Pot) = s1_MRC_HestN10/Parameters.Simulations;
s2_tot_MRC_HestN10 (Sim,Pot) = s2_MRC_HestN10/Parameters.Simulations;
s3_tot_MRC_HestN10 (Sim,Pot) = s3_MRC_HestN10/Parameters.Simulations;
s4_tot_MRC_HestN10 (Sim,Pot) = s4_MRC_HestN10/Parameters.Simulations;
%MRC Hest5
s1_tot_MRC_HestN5 (Sim,Pot) = s1_MRC_HestN5/Parameters.Simulations;
s2_tot_MRC_HestN5 (Sim,Pot) = s2_MRC_HestN5/Parameters.Simulations;
s3_tot_MRC_HestN5 (Sim,Pot) = s3_MRC_HestN5/Parameters.Simulations;
s4_tot_MRC_HestN5 (Sim,Pot) = s4_MRC_HestN5/Parameters.Simulations;
%ZF Hest50
s1_tot_ZF_HestN50 (Sim,Pot) = s1_ZF_HestN50/Parameters.Simulations;
s2_tot_ZF_HestN50 (Sim,Pot) = s2_ZF_HestN50/Parameters.Simulations;
s3_tot_ZF_HestN50 (Sim,Pot) = s3_ZF_HestN50/Parameters.Simulations;
s4_tot_ZF_HestN50 (Sim,Pot) = s4_ZF_HestN50/Parameters.Simulations;
%ZF Hest10
s1_tot_ZF_HestN10 (Sim,Pot) = s1_ZF_HestN10/Parameters.Simulations;
s2_tot_ZF_HestN10 (Sim,Pot) = s2_ZF_HestN10/Parameters.Simulations;
s3_tot_ZF_HestN10 (Sim,Pot) = s3_ZF_HestN10/Parameters.Simulations;
s4_tot_ZF_HestN10 (Sim,Pot) = s4_ZF_HestN10/Parameters.Simulations;
%ZF Hest50
s1_tot_ZF_HestN5 (Sim,Pot) = s1_ZF_HestN5/Parameters.Simulations;
s2_tot_ZF_HestN5 (Sim,Pot) = s2_ZF_HestN5/Parameters.Simulations;
s3_tot_ZF_HestN5 (Sim,Pot) = s3_ZF_HestN5/Parameters.Simulations;
s4_tot_ZF_HestN5 (Sim,Pot) = s4_ZF_HestN5/Parameters.Simulations;

end
end
%% ...
-----
%Only is executed if Analytical approach procedure is selected
if Parameters.AnalyticalChoice == 1

    ResultAnalytical.MutualInfo_MRC = mean(DataAnalytical.MutualInfo_MRC_tot);
    ResultAnalytical.MutualInfo_ZF = mean(DataAnalytical.MutualInfo_ZF_tot);
    assignin('base','Result',ResultAnalytical)
end
%% ...
-----
%The ratio of symbols estimated of each channel simulation is averaged
P1_MRC_Full_CSI = mean(s1_tot_MRC_Full_CSI);
P2_MRC_Full_CSI = mean(s2_tot_MRC_Full_CSI);
P3_MRC_Full_CSI = mean(s3_tot_MRC_Full_CSI);
P4_MRC_Full_CSI = mean(s4_tot_MRC_Full_CSI);

P1_ZF_Full_CSI = mean(s1_tot_ZF_Full_CSI);
P2_ZF_Full_CSI = mean(s2_tot_ZF_Full_CSI);
P3_ZF_Full_CSI = mean(s3_tot_ZF_Full_CSI);
P4_ZF_Full_CSI = mean(s4_tot_ZF_Full_CSI);

P1_MRC_HestN50 = mean(s1_tot_MRC_HestN50);
P2_MRC_HestN50 = mean(s2_tot_MRC_HestN50);
P3_MRC_HestN50 = mean(s3_tot_MRC_HestN50);
P4_MRC_HestN50 = mean(s4_tot_MRC_HestN50);

P1_MRC_HestN10 = mean(s1_tot_MRC_HestN10);
P2_MRC_HestN10 = mean(s2_tot_MRC_HestN10);
P3_MRC_HestN10 = mean(s3_tot_MRC_HestN10);
P4_MRC_HestN10 = mean(s4_tot_MRC_HestN10);

```

```

P1_MRC_HestN5 = mean(s1_tot_MRC_HestN5);
P2_MRC_HestN5 = mean(s2_tot_MRC_HestN5);
P3_MRC_HestN5 = mean(s3_tot_MRC_HestN5);
P4_MRC_HestN5 = mean(s4_tot_MRC_HestN5);

P1_ZF_HestN50 = mean(s1_tot_ZF_HestN50);
P2_ZF_HestN50 = mean(s2_tot_ZF_HestN50);
P3_ZF_HestN50 = mean(s3_tot_ZF_HestN50);
P4_ZF_HestN50 = mean(s4_tot_ZF_HestN50);

P1_ZF_HestN10 = mean(s1_tot_ZF_HestN10);
P2_ZF_HestN10 = mean(s2_tot_ZF_HestN10);
P3_ZF_HestN10 = mean(s3_tot_ZF_HestN10);
P4_ZF_HestN10 = mean(s4_tot_ZF_HestN10);

P1_ZF_HestN5 = mean(s1_tot_ZF_HestN5);
P2_ZF_HestN5 = mean(s2_tot_ZF_HestN5);
P3_ZF_HestN5 = mean(s3_tot_ZF_HestN5);
P4_ZF_HestN5 = mean(s4_tot_ZF_HestN5);
%% ...
-----
P_Xk=0.25;%qpsk equally distributed
%%
P_MRC_Full_CSI = [P1_MRC_Full_CSI; P2_MRC_Full_CSI; P3_MRC_Full_CSI; P4_MRC_Full_CSI];
P_ZF_Full_CSI = [P1_ZF_Full_CSI; P2_ZF_Full_CSI; P3_ZF_Full_CSI; P4_ZF_Full_CSI];
P_MRC_HestN50 = [P1_MRC_HestN50; P2_MRC_HestN50; P3_MRC_HestN50; P4_MRC_HestN50];
P_MRC_HestN10 = [P1_MRC_HestN10; P2_MRC_HestN10; P3_MRC_HestN10; P4_MRC_HestN10];
P_MRC_HestN5 = [P1_MRC_HestN5; P2_MRC_HestN5; P3_MRC_HestN5; P4_MRC_HestN5];
P_ZF_HestN50 = [P1_ZF_HestN50; P2_ZF_HestN50; P3_ZF_HestN50; P4_ZF_HestN50];
P_ZF_HestN10 = [P1_ZF_HestN10; P2_ZF_HestN10; P3_ZF_HestN10; P4_ZF_HestN10];
P_ZF_HestN5 = [P1_ZF_HestN5; P2_ZF_HestN5; P3_ZF_HestN5; P4_ZF_HestN5];
%% ...
-----
%Mutual information computation using equation (10) and Monte Carlo simulations
for i=1:length(Parameters.NoisePowerMI)

    ResultMonteCarlo.MI_MRC_Full_CSI(i) = ...
        4*sum(P_MRC_Full_CSI(:,i)*P_Xk.*(log2(P_MRC_Full_CSI(:,i)/sum(P_MRC_Full_CSI(:,i)*P_Xk))));
    ResultMonteCarlo.MI_ZF_Full_CSI(i) = ...
        4*sum(P_ZF_Full_CSI(:,i)*P_Xk.*(log2(P_ZF_Full_CSI(:,i)/sum(P_ZF_Full_CSI(:,i)*P_Xk))));
    ResultMonteCarlo.MI_MRC_HestN50(i) = ...
        4*sum(P_MRC_HestN50(:,i)*P_Xk.*(log2(P_MRC_HestN50(:,i)/sum(P_MRC_HestN50(:,i)*P_Xk))));
    ResultMonteCarlo.MI_MRC_HestN10(i) = ...
        4*sum(P_MRC_HestN10(:,i)*P_Xk.*(log2(P_MRC_HestN10(:,i)/sum(P_MRC_HestN10(:,i)*P_Xk))));
    ResultMonteCarlo.MI_MRC_HestN5(i) = ...
        4*sum(P_MRC_HestN5(:,i)*P_Xk.*(log2(P_MRC_HestN5(:,i)/sum(P_MRC_HestN5(:,i)*P_Xk))));
    ResultMonteCarlo.MI_ZF_HestN50(i) = ...
        4*sum(P_ZF_HestN50(:,i)*P_Xk.*(log2(P_ZF_HestN50(:,i)/sum(P_ZF_HestN50(:,i)*P_Xk))));
    ResultMonteCarlo.MI_ZF_HestN10(i) = ...
        4*sum(P_ZF_HestN10(:,i)*P_Xk.*(log2(P_ZF_HestN10(:,i)/sum(P_ZF_HestN10(:,i)*P_Xk))));
    ResultMonteCarlo.MI_ZF_HestN5(i) = ...
        4*sum(P_ZF_HestN5(:,i)*P_Xk.*(log2(P_ZF_HestN5(:,i)/sum(P_ZF_HestN5(:,i)*P_Xk))));
end
assignin('base','Result',ResultMonteCarlo)
%plot
Plot_MI

```

Mutual Information Analytical Approach:

```

%%
%We use equation (15) to compute the interferences between users in each antenna
User = 1;%We select a single user which we use to compute the analytical approach

```

```

h_ik          = H_Full_CSI;
h_ik(:,User) = 0; %It eliminates the user who is not considered interferent
Sigma_I       = Parameters.P_tx*sum(abs(h_ik).^2,2);%it is computed the interference noise with the ...
              equation (15)
%Probabilities Pic (equations 16-19) for each antenna
Data.P_i1 = zeros(Parameters.M,1);
Data.P_i2 = zeros(Parameters.M,1);
Data.P_i3 = zeros(Parameters.M,1);
Data.P_i4 = zeros(Parameters.M,1);

H_x = H_Full_CSI(:,User);%It is selected the channel for the chosen user
x_k = x(User);%it is selcted the symbol transmitted by the user selected
for i = 1:Parameters.M %it is compted Pic

    Data.P_i1(i) = 0.5*erfc((-sqrt(Parameters.P_tx)*real(H_x(i) * ...
        x_k))/(sqrt(n.power+Sigma_I(i))))...
        *0.5*erfc((-sqrt(Parameters.P_tx)*imag(H_x(i) * x_k))/(sqrt(n.power+Sigma_I(i))));

    Data.P_i2(i) = 0.5*erfc((-sqrt(Parameters.P_tx)*real(H_x(i) * ...
        x_k))/(sqrt(n.power+Sigma_I(i))))...
        *(1-(0.5*erfc((-sqrt(Parameters.P_tx)*imag(H_x(i) * ...
        x_k))/(sqrt(n.power+Sigma_I(i)))))...);

    Data.P_i3(i) = (1-(0.5*erfc((-sqrt(Parameters.P_tx)*real(H_x(i) * ...
        x_k))/(sqrt(n.power+Sigma_I(i)))))...
        *(1-(0.5*erfc((-sqrt(Parameters.P_tx)*imag(H_x(i) * ...
        x_k))/(sqrt(n.power+Sigma_I(i)))))...);

    Data.P_i4(i) = (1-(0.5*erfc((-sqrt(Parameters.P_tx)*real(H_x(i) * ...
        x_k))/(sqrt(n.power+Sigma_I(i)))))...
        *0.5*erfc((-sqrt(Parameters.P_tx)*imag(H_x(i) * x_k))/(sqrt(n.power+Sigma_I(i))));

end

A_tot_ZF = cat(3, A_ZF_Full_CSI, A_ZF_HestN50, A_ZF_HestN10, A_ZF_HestN5);%Multidimensional array ...
          wich contain all the ZF receive filters

for Sel = 1:4%sel is used to select the channels and receive filters within the multidimensional array
    H = H_tot(:,User, Sel);%it's selected the channel (only for the requiered user)
    A = A_tot_ZF(User, :, Sel);
%preallocate vectors
Sigma_MRC_tot = zeros(Parameters.M,1);
Mu_MRC_tot    = zeros(Parameters.M,1);
Mu_ZF_tot     = zeros(Parameters.M,1);
Sigma_ZF_tot  = zeros(Parameters.M,1);
for i = 1:Parameters.M%it is computed the Mu and Sigma of the equation (12) for each antenna

    Sigma_MRC_tot(i) = (abs(H(i))^2)/(norm(H(:))^4) * (2-(abs(Data.P_i1(i)*Parameters.Symbols(1) + ...
        Data.P_i2(i)*Parameters.Symbols(2) + Data.P_i3(i)*Parameters.Symbols(3) + ...
        Data.P_i4(i)*Parameters.Symbols(4))^2);
    Mu_MRC_tot(i)    = (conj(H(i))/(norm(H(:))^2) * (Data.P_i1(i)*Parameters.Symbols(1) + ...
        Data.P_i2(i)*Parameters.Symbols(2) + Data.P_i3(i)*Parameters.Symbols(3) + ...
        Data.P_i4(i)*Parameters.Symbols(4));
    Sigma_ZF_tot(i) = abs(A(i))^2 * (2-(abs(Data.P_i1(i)*Parameters.Symbols(1) + ...
        Data.P_i2(i)*Parameters.Symbols(2) + Data.P_i3(i)*Parameters.Symbols(3) + ...
        Data.P_i4(i)*Parameters.Symbols(4))^2);
    Mu_ZF_tot(i)    = A(i) * (Data.P_i1(i)*Parameters.Symbols(1) + ...
        Data.P_i2(i)*Parameters.Symbols(2) + Data.P_i3(i)*Parameters.Symbols(3) + ...
        Data.P_i4(i)*Parameters.Symbols(4));

end

%The values of Mu and Sigma for each antenna needs to be added in order to
%obtain the PDF showed in (12)
Data.Sigma_12_MRC = sum(Sigma_MRC_tot);
Data.Sigma_12_ZF  = sum(Sigma_ZF_tot);

```

```

Data.Mu_12_MRC = sum(Mu_MRC_tot);
Data.Mu_12_ZF = sum(Mu_ZF_tot);
%it is computed the probabilities of estimate each symbol
P1_MRC = qfunc(-real(Data.Mu_12_MRC)/sqrt(Data.Sigma_12_MRC/2)) * ...
        qfunc(-imag(Data.Mu_12_MRC)/sqrt(Data.Sigma_12_MRC/2)); %con el /2 tenemos en cuenta la parte ...
        real e imaginaria
P2_MRC = qfunc(-real(Data.Mu_12_MRC)/sqrt(Data.Sigma_12_MRC/2)) * ...
        (1-qfunc(-imag(Data.Mu_12_MRC)/sqrt(Data.Sigma_12_MRC/2)));
P3_MRC = (1-qfunc(-real(Data.Mu_12_MRC)/sqrt(Data.Sigma_12_MRC/2))) * ...
        (1-qfunc(-imag(Data.Mu_12_MRC)/sqrt(Data.Sigma_12_MRC/2)));
P4_MRC = (1-qfunc(-real(Data.Mu_12_MRC)/sqrt(Data.Sigma_12_MRC/2))) * ...
        qfunc(-imag(Data.Mu_12_MRC)/sqrt(Data.Sigma_12_MRC/2));
P1_ZF = qfunc(-real(Data.Mu_12_ZF)/sqrt(Data.Sigma_12_ZF/2)) * ...
        qfunc(-imag(Data.Mu_12_ZF)/sqrt(Data.Sigma_12_ZF/2));
P2_ZF = qfunc(-real(Data.Mu_12_ZF)/sqrt(Data.Sigma_12_ZF/2)) * ...
        (1-qfunc(-imag(Data.Mu_12_ZF)/sqrt(Data.Sigma_12_ZF/2)));
P3_ZF = (1-qfunc(-real(Data.Mu_12_ZF)/sqrt(Data.Sigma_12_ZF/2))) * ...
        (1-qfunc(-imag(Data.Mu_12_ZF)/sqrt(Data.Sigma_12_ZF/2)));
P4_ZF = (1-qfunc(-real(Data.Mu_12_ZF)/sqrt(Data.Sigma_12_ZF/2))) * ...
        qfunc(-imag(Data.Mu_12_ZF)/sqrt(Data.Sigma_12_ZF/2));

Data.P_MRC = [P1_MRC P2_MRC P3_MRC P4_MRC];
Data.P_ZF = [P1_ZF P2_ZF P3_ZF P4_ZF];
P_Xk = 0.25;%QPSK uniformilly distributed, 4 symbols all equiprobables

DataAnalytical.MutualInfo_MRC_tot(Sim2,Pot,Sel) = ...
        4*sum(Data.P_MRC*P_Xk.*(log2(Data.P_MRC/sum(Data.P_MRC*P_Xk))));
DataAnalytical.MutualInfo_ZF_tot(Sim2,Pot,Sel) = ...
        4*sum(Data.P_ZF*P_Xk.*(log2(Data.P_ZF/sum(Data.P_ZF*P_Xk))));
end
assignin('base','Data',DataAnalytical)

```

Mutual Information plot function:

```

%plots for Monte Carlo simulations
if Parameters.MonteCarloChoice == 1
    if Parameters.ChannelOption == 1
        figure
        plot(Parameters.SNR_MI_dB,ResultMonteCarlo.MI_MRC_Full_CSI,'-bs');
        hold on
        plot(Parameters.SNR_MI_dB,ResultMonteCarlo.MI_MRC_HestN50,'--bs');
        hold on
        plot(Parameters.SNR_MI_dB,ResultMonteCarlo.MI_MRC_HestN10,':bs');
        hold on
        plot(Parameters.SNR_MI_dB,ResultMonteCarlo.MI_MRC_HestN5,'-bs');
        hold on
        plot(Parameters.SNR_MI_dB,ResultMonteCarlo.MI_ZF_Full_CSI,'-rs');
        hold on
        plot(Parameters.SNR_MI_dB,ResultMonteCarlo.MI_ZF_HestN50,'--rs');
        hold on
        plot(Parameters.SNR_MI_dB,ResultMonteCarlo.MI_ZF_HestN10,':rs');
        hold on
        plot(Parameters.SNR_MI_dB,ResultMonteCarlo.MI_ZF_HestN5,'-rs');
        legend('MRC, Full CSI', 'MRC, Channel Estimation, N=50K', 'MRC, Channel Estimation, N=10K',...
            'MRC, Channel Estimation, N=5K', 'ZF, full CSI', 'ZF, Channel Estimation, N=50K',...
            'ZF, Channel Estimation, N=10K', 'ZF, Channel Estimation, N=5')
        axis([-20 10 0 2])
        grid on
        xlabel('SNR (dB)')
        ylabel('Mutual Information per user (bit/channel use)')
    else

```

```

plot(Parameters.SNR_MI_dB,ResultMonteCarlo.MI_MRC_Full_CSI,'-bs');
hold on
plot(Parameters.SNR_MI_dB,ResultMonteCarlo.MI_MRC_HestN50,'--bs');
hold on
plot(Parameters.SNR_MI_dB,ResultMonteCarlo.MI_MRC_HestN10,':bs');
hold on
plot(Parameters.SNR_MI_dB,ResultMonteCarlo.MI_MRC_HestN5,'-.bs');
hold on
plot(Parameters.SNR_MI_dB,ResultMonteCarlo.MI_ZF_Full_CSI,'-rs');
hold on
plot(Parameters.SNR_MI_dB,ResultMonteCarlo.MI_ZF_HestN50,'--rs');
hold on
plot(Parameters.SNR_MI_dB,ResultMonteCarlo.MI_ZF_HestN10,':rs');
hold on
plot(Parameters.SNR_MI_dB,ResultMonteCarlo.MI_ZF_HestN5,'-.rs');
legend('MRC, Full CSI', 'MRC, Channel Estimation, N=50M', 'MRC, Channel Estimation, N=10M',...
'MRC, Channel Estimation, N=5M', 'ZF, full CSI', 'ZF, Channel Estimation, N=50M',...
'ZF, Channel Estimation, N=10M', 'ZF, Channel Estimation, N=5M')
axis([-20 10 0 2])
grid on
xlabel('SNR (dB)')
ylabel('Mutual Information per user (bit/channel use)')
end
end
%plots for Analytical approach
if Parameters.AnalyticalChoice == 1
if Parameters.ChannelOption == 1
figure
plot(Parameters.SNR_MI_dB,ResultAnalytical.MutualInfo_MRC(:, :, 1), '-bs');
hold on
plot(Parameters.SNR_MI_dB,ResultAnalytical.MutualInfo_MRC(:, :, 2), '--bs');
hold on
plot(Parameters.SNR_MI_dB,ResultAnalytical.MutualInfo_MRC(:, :, 3), ':bs');
hold on
plot(Parameters.SNR_MI_dB,ResultAnalytical.MutualInfo_MRC(:, :, 4), '-.bs');
legend('MRC, Full CSI', 'MRC, Channel Estimation, N=50K', 'MRC, Channel Estimation, N=10K',...
'MRC, Channel Estimation, N=5K', 'ZF, full CSI', 'ZF, Channel Estimation, N=50K',...
'ZF, Channel Estimation, N=10K', 'ZF, Channel Estimation, N=5')
axis([-20 10 0 2])
grid on
xlabel('SNR (dB)')
ylabel('Mutual Information per user (bit/channel use)')
else
figure
plot(Parameters.SNR_MI_dB,ResultAnalytical.MutualInfo_MRC(:, :, 1), '-bs');
hold on
plot(Parameters.SNR_MI_dB,ResultAnalytical.MutualInfo_MRC(:, :, 2), '--bs');
hold on
plot(Parameters.SNR_MI_dB,ResultAnalytical.MutualInfo_MRC(:, :, 3), ':bs');
hold on
plot(Parameters.SNR_MI_dB,ResultAnalytical.MutualInfo_MRC(:, :, 4), '-.bs');
legend('MRC, Full CSI', 'MRC, Channel Estimation, N=50M', 'MRC, Channel Estimation, N=10M',...
'MRC, Channel Estimation, N=5M', 'ZF, full CSI', 'ZF, Channel Estimation, N=50M',...
'ZF, Channel Estimation, N=10M', 'ZF, Channel Estimation, N=5M')
axis([-20 10 0 2])
grid on
xlabel('SNR (dB)')
ylabel('Mutual Information per user (bit/channel use)')
end
end
if Parameters.AnalyticalChoice == 1 && Parameters.MonteCarloChoice == 1
%figures to compare the analytical approach with the numerical computation
figure(3)
plot(Parameters.SNR_MI_dB,ResultAnalytical.MutualInfo_ZF(:, :, 1));

```

```
hold on
plot(Parameters.SNR_MI_dB, ResultMonteCarlo.MI_MRC.Full_CSI);
xlabel('SNR (dB)')
axis([-20 10 1.2 2])
grid on
ylabel('Symbol Error Rate per user')
legend('Analytical', 'Numerical')
end
```

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